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Estimating the Mutual Information for Time-Varying Signals in Cellular Signaling Networks

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Berechnung der Transinformation für zeitabhängige Signale in biochemischen Netzwerken

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1 Introduction

Noise is inherent across diverse biological systems and remains relevant at all biological scales. From *stochastic gene expression* and random *action potential spikes* in neuronal networks at the cellular scale to the *development of multi-cellular organisms* all the way to the *variations in population level* of competing species in whole ecosystems, we find examples of processes which can only be described precisely by taking into account noise as an intrinsic feature [1–5]. In this thesis we focus on the smaller end of this scale, namely on the stochastic description of *biochemical networks*. These comprise among others *gene expression*, *gene regulatory networks*, and *cell signaling* networks, all of which exhibit noise due to small copy numbers of their components. Additionally, since biological processes often happen out of equilibrium even macroscopic quantities can exhibit large fluctuations. The main source of noise at the cellular level may be fluctuations in *gene expression* which propagate to higher levels of biological organization [5]. The abundance of noise in all these systems leads to the question of how cells can reliably make correct decisions, even in complex and changing environments and how cells are able to *encode* the information about their environment using biochemical networks.

To successfully function, cells must generally correctly react to environmental changes. This requires processing the environmental cues they receive through their receptors and thereby filtering out the useful information from the noisy signal. The processing of information through biochemical networks can be quite elaborate with individual network components being able to perform analogous functions like silicon computational devices such as transistors [6]. It is thus tempting to think that optimization of information processing drives the evolution of cellular signaling networks. To understand information processing from the cell's point of view we employ the very general framework of *information theory* which was originally developed to address questions of the reliability of telecommunications [7].

In this thesis we study novel methods to understand information processing capabilities of biochemical networks from computational simulations. To this end we need to model the cell sig-

naling network and the cellular environment using *stochastic differential equations* and simulate the biochemical network response to different stimuli. Using information theory we can analyze the results of these simulations and estimate abstract quantities like the amount of information that the biochemical networks processes on average.

1.1 Goal of the Thesis

This thesis presents an overview over the work performed throughout a master's project. Its aim was to design an algorithm for the computational estimation of information processing efficiency of biochemical signaling networks. Therefore, the first goal of the thesis is to introduce the reader to the stochastic description of biochemical networks with a special focus on information processing. We continue by presenting a Monte Carlo algorithm to compute the amount of information that a chemical network retains of a time-varying signal. As was discovered throughout the project, this algorithm in its simplest form cannot give accurate estimates of the amount of processed information. Consequently, this thesis intends to highlight the reasons for the algorithm's problems, and we discuss ways to overcome them. Hence, while the solutions we formulate to fix the estimate certainly are very promising it has to be noted that this thesis represents work that is still in progress. Thus, a final goal of the present thesis is to give a perspective about future developments that will have to be done to complete the work presented here.

1.2 Structure of the Thesis

We begin the second chapter by giving a general introduction of stochastic descriptions of biochemical systems and the core concepts of information theory that we will make use of. From basic identities of probability theory we heuristically derive the chemical master equation and other important mathematical identities that will be used throughout the later chapters. Crucially, the last section of chapter 2 contains a detailed analysis of a simple biochemical network that will be the main object of study throughout the rest of the thesis. Therefore, the goal of the second chapter is to provide a useful overview of existing knowledge, and setting the stage for the remaining chapters rather than providing novel results itself.

In the third chapter we then apply the main results from chapter 2 to develop a computational estimate of the information transmission performance for a large class of biochemical systems. We compare estimates done using this novel method with analytical results and find large discrepancies. After performing a detailed analysis we argue that the main issue is the computation of a high-dimensional integral in trajectory space.

Therefore, the fourth chapter completely focuses on efficient methods of computing such a high-dimensional integral. We will review different approaches found in the literature to numerically perform integrals. The most convincing methods originate from statistical physics. To be able to make use of these, we demonstrate that our integral can be re-cast in terms of the canonical ensemble such that we can make use of algorithms originally designed for statistical ensembles. While this work is not done yet, we will give some useful ideas that need to be explored to complete this work.

The thesis ends with a summary of the main results and a conclusion focusing on future work.

2 Modeling Cell Signaling Networks as Information Processing Devices

Information theory has been successfully used in biology to study cellular communication, embryonic development and other biological systems [8,9]. Notably, there are many parallels between biological signal processing and *noisy channels* which are used for example to describe information transmission across a telephone line. Hence, a crucial feature of information theory is that its results are broadly applicable, irrespective of the nature of the communication channel or the medium used to transmit a signal. The communication channel merely describes any kind of abstract device that processes an *input* in a probabilistic way to yield a corresponding *output*. It turns out that the study of information transmission through such a channel is closely related to the study of noise. The amount of noise introduced by a communication channel sets an upper bound to the amount of data that can be transmitted through it, known as the *channel capacity* [10]. Consequently, the output can be described as a deterministic, lossless transformation of the input *plus* some random noise from the channel which leads to a loss of information. Note that in biological systems the signal itself is typically a fluctuating quantity such that the randomness in the output is a combination of the channel noise and the intrinsic fluctuations of the signal. Since in cell signaling both, input and output are time-varying quantities we require a description of our system that allows for deterministic *and* stochastic time evolution. We will therefore continue with an overview of techniques for stochastic modeling of biological networks.

Differential equations are generally extremely useful to describe any kind of system that evolves deterministically. Therefore, it is natural to try to extend the framework of *ordinary differential equations* (ODEs) to also include the ability to describe the effects of noise. Historically, this approach to modeling stochastic dynamics has first been formulated heuristically by Langevin to describe *Brownian motion* [11]. Later the theory of *stochastic differential equations* (SDEs) was put on solid mathematical footing by Itô and Stratonovich through the development of *stochastic calculus* which has been successfully used for applications in physics, biology, economics and

others [12,13]. The solutions to SDEs are not ordinary functions like for ODEs but *stochastic processes* that describe the probabilities for the system to be in any state for every instant in time. Consequently, a stochastic process contains the probabilities for any possible individual sequence of states in time, i.e. the probabilities for individual *trajectories*. Since SDEs model the noise in a system, information theoretic concepts like the *entropy* and the *mutual information*—which we are going to use to understand information transmission in cell signaling—can be applied to stochastic processes. While SDEs can be formulated to describe the evolution of biochemical networks in a discrete state space it is generally more useful to use a less general but simpler *chemical master equation* for these kinds of problems [14].

The chemical master equation is a description of a subset of stochastic processes by deriving the *time-evolution* of the probability distribution over the discrete state space. I.e. instead of describing the stochastic change to an individual state at a given time it focuses on the *deterministic* evolution of the whole probability distribution over all states. Conveniently, for a given set of chemical reactions that form a reaction network, we can easily find the corresponding chemical master equation that describes the stochastic dynamics of this network given some assumptions of homogeneity. The stochastic process that emerges of this formulation describes the probabilities for the individual counts of all species and how these probabilities change with time. The ease with which the chemical master equation allows the construction of a stochastic process for any kind of biochemical network makes the idea very attractive to try to use *master equations* as the basis for information theoretic computations. If we can *solve* the master equation we in principle have access to all stochastic (and therefore information theoretic) properties of the corresponding biochemical network. E.g. in [15] it is shown how by analytically solving some very simple biochemical networks (using some approximations) it is possible to compute many quantities related to information transmission for time-varying signals and corresponding responses of these networks.

In most cases however, chemical master equations cannot be solved analytically and instead require computing averages for ensembles of *stochastic trajectories*. For instance, in Shannon's information theory the amount of communicated information is not a function of individual signal-response pairs but an averaged quantity that depends on the probability of seeing *any* random signal-response-pair. Hence, computationally efficient generation of stochastic realizations for a given master equation is a central requirement for the exact computation of information processing in chemical networks. A very well known algorithm for the *exact* generation of trajectories from a given initial condition is the *stochastic simulation algorithm* (SSA) also known by the

name of its inventor as the *Gillespie algorithm* [16]. The most widely used variant is the *direct Gillespie method* which works by alternatingly a) computing the time during which no reactions happen and b) choosing which of the available reactions to perform next. As a result we generate a list of times when some reaction happens and a corresponding list of reactions that specifies the exact trajectory that was generated. This algorithm works quite well in practice and is also used for the work presented in this thesis. It is still worth mentioning that for systems that evolve at different time scales simultaneously, the direct Gillespie method can be computationally inefficient since by its design it always operates at the smallest time scale. Therefore, there have been developed further trajectory-generation algorithms that can generate *approximately* correct trajectories by accumulating various reactions into a single time step such as the τ -leap method [17].

In summary, there has been considerable effort to understand how cells receive, process and make use of information that their environments provide. A key aspect in this endeavor is the stochastic modeling of biological processes that take into account the natural fluctuations in these systems. In the following sections of this chapter we explain in more detail how we specifically model biochemical signaling networks in cells and how to understand information transmission in that context.

2.1 Information Theory in the Context of Cellular Signaling Networks

We begin by introducing information theoretic quantities like the *mutual information* and the *information rate* as relevant properties to understand optimality criteria for biochemical signaling networks.

2.1.1 Mutual Information as an Efficiency Measure in Cell signaling

In a general sense, cells sense chemical *signals* from their environment e.g. through receptors on their membrane. These signals provide the cell with important information e.g. about current environmental conditions, their position inside a structure or the location of food. To translate the signal into a useful response (such as expressing a certain gene or changing movement direction) cells have evolved biochemical signaling networks that recognize and process the signals. We use a general description of the cell that is depicted in fig. 2.1 where the signal acts as the input of the

Figure 2.1: Abstracting cell signaling as an information channel. The channel’s input is an environmental signal that the cell needs to respond to. The signal processing happens through a biochemical network which “computes” a response which is the output of the information channel. The mutual information between signals and responses quantifies the cell’s ability to discern between different signals and choose appropriate responses.

information channel. The processing of the signal happens through a biochemical network which is assumed to be known. The stochastic dynamics of the copy numbers of the individual species in the biochemical network act as the “result” of the computation and represent the response of the cell to the signal.

For any given signal there are many stochastically possible responses. Conversely, for any given response there is a range of signals that could have produced it. Both of these statements of uncertainty can be quantified using a single concept: the *mutual information*. In information theoretic terms we quantify the *uncertainty* of a random variable \mathcal{S} by the *entropy*

$$H(\mathcal{S}) = - \int_{\sigma(\mathcal{S})} ds P(\mathbf{s}) \ln P(\mathbf{s}) \quad (2.1)$$

where $\sigma(\mathcal{S})$ is the set of possible realizations of \mathcal{S} and we use $P(\mathbf{s})$ to denote the probability (density) of \mathbf{s} with respect to the distribution of \mathcal{S} . If \mathcal{S} describes the signal then a large entropy signifies that there is a large range of possible signals that could be expected by the cell. Now given the response \mathbf{x} to a signal \mathbf{s} , we expect \mathbf{x} to contain information about \mathbf{s} such that the uncertainty about the signal is reduced. The conditional entropy $H(\mathcal{S}|\mathcal{X})$ denotes the *average*

remaining uncertainty of a signal after observing the response, hence it reads

$$H(\mathcal{S}|\mathcal{X}) = - \int_{\sigma(\mathcal{X})} d\mathbf{x} P(\mathbf{x}) \int_{\sigma(\mathcal{S})} d\mathbf{s} P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}) \ln P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}). \quad (2.2)$$

$P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})$ is the conditional distribution of the signals for a given response \mathbf{x} which encodes the transmission characteristics of the communication channel. So we have eq. (2.1) which describes the distribution of signals and eq. (2.2) which describes how information is processed. Combining eqns. (2.1) and (2.2) we can express the *average* amount of information gained on the signal by observing the response

$$I(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{X}) = H(\mathcal{S}) - H(\mathcal{S}|\mathcal{X}) = \int_{\sigma(\mathcal{X})} d\mathbf{x} P(\mathbf{x}) \int_{\sigma(\mathcal{S})} d\mathbf{s} P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}) \ln \frac{P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})}{P(\mathbf{s})} \quad (2.3)$$

which is precisely the *mutual information between \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X}* . It depends on both, characteristics of the communication channel and the statistics of the input signal. Notably the $I(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{X})$ is symmetric under exchange of \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} such that we can express it as

$$I(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{X}) = H(\mathcal{X}) - H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S}) = \int_{\sigma(\mathcal{S})} d\mathbf{s} P(\mathbf{s}) \int_{\sigma(\mathcal{X})} d\mathbf{x} P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) \ln \frac{P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})}{P(\mathbf{x})}, \quad (2.4)$$

resulting in a more useful formula for the Monte-Carlo estimation of the MI. Therefore, on average, a response reduces the uncertainty about the signal by exactly the same amount that a signal reduces the uncertainty about the possible responses.

2.1.2 Information Transmission for Time-Varying Signals

Biochemical networks may store information about the signal in the time-dependency of the response, for example in cellular Ca^{2+} signaling information seems to be encoded in the timing and duration of Calcium bursts [15,18,19]. For the case where the signal can be regarded as slowly changing with respect to the response, Cepeda-Humerez, et. al. propose a Monte-Carlo technique for the estimation of the MI that includes information that is stored in the full temporal dynamics of the response [20]. As described in their work, that method is limited to situations that are well-described by a finite number of discrete signals.

Often however, biochemical networks not only respond to instantaneous signal levels but also to changes in the signal over time. Therefore, we build on the technique in [20] by extending it

to allow for time-varying, stochastic signals as well. In this way we aim to find a novel way to compute the MI for time-varying signals *and* responses for general biochemical networks.

The study of time-varying quantities motivates the definition of the *information rate* which is the asymptotic rate at which the MI between signal and response increases [15]

$$I_R = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{I(\mathcal{S}_T, \mathcal{X}_T)}{T} \quad (2.5)$$

where \mathcal{S}_T and \mathcal{X}_T are random variables over *trajectories* of length T . By *trajectories* we denote an entire time-trace of the signal or response, instead of singular values at specific times. Since eq. (2.5) describes the information gained by the cell in a unit time interval it may be an important quantity for the cell to optimize for.

Hence, we find that the fundamental building block for the computation of the information rate at the cellular level is the estimation of the mutual information between trajectories of finite length. In the remainder of this thesis, we describe methods to compute the mutual information between trajectories $\mathcal{S}_T, \mathcal{X}_T$ based on a stochastic model of the biochemical signaling network.

2.1.3 Chemical Master Equation

As a model for the biochemical processing that takes place inside a cell we suppose that all interactions can be described by a chemical networks composed of different molecular species and reactions between them. Such networks can be described by a *chemical master equation* which makes it possible to compute all the probabilities associated with the time-evolution of such a system.

For illustrative purposes, let's consider a highly simplified model of gene expression consisting of two components and four reactions

Here S and X are arbitrary chemical species whose particle counts we want to describe stochastically. The constants $\kappa, \lambda, \rho, \mu$ determine the rates at which the individual reactions occur. Hence,

for every signal particle there is a constant rate ρ to be sensed by the cell which triggers the creation of an X . Additionally, X particles decays by themselves over time with a per-particle rate of μ . Assuming a well stirred system in thermal equilibrium, it can be shown that the probabilities for the individual reactions happening at least once in the time interval $[t, t + \delta t]$ are

$$\begin{aligned} p_{[t, t + \delta t]}^{(\kappa)} &= \kappa \delta t + \mathcal{O}(\delta t^2) \\ p_{[t, t + \delta t]}^{(\lambda)}(s) &= s \lambda \delta t + \mathcal{O}(\delta t^2) \\ p_{[t, t + \delta t]}^{(\rho)}(s) &= s \rho \delta t + \mathcal{O}(\delta t^2) \\ p_{[t, t + \delta t]}^{(\mu)}(x) &= x \mu \delta t + \mathcal{O}(\delta t^2) \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

where s and x denote the particle numbers of the respective species at time t . Consequently, the probability for *any* of the reactions to occur at least once in the time interval $[t, t + \delta t]$ is

$$p_{[t, t + \delta t]}(s, x) = (\kappa + s \lambda + s \rho + x \mu) \delta t + \mathcal{O}(\delta t^2) \quad (2.8)$$

Using these expressions we can write down the so-called *chemical master equation* for this network. Let $P_{s,x}(t)$ be the probability that the system is in state (s, x) at time t . Assuming that at most one reaction happens in the small time-interval $[t, t + \delta t]$ we can use the transition probabilities from eqns. (2.7) and (2.8) to write

$$\begin{aligned} P_{s,x}(t + \delta t) &= p_{[t, t + \delta t]}^{(\kappa)} P_{s-1,x}(t) \\ &\quad + p_{[t, t + \delta t]}^{(\lambda)}(s+1) P_{s+1,x}(t) \\ &\quad + p_{[t, t + \delta t]}^{(\rho)}(s) P_{s,x-1}(t) \\ &\quad + p_{[t, t + \delta t]}^{(\mu)}(x+1) P_{s,x+1}(t) \\ &\quad + [1 - p_{[t, t + \delta t]}(s, x)] P_{s,x}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

and by taking the limit $\delta t \rightarrow 0$ we arrive at the chemical master equation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P_{s,x}(t)}{\partial t} &= \lim_{\delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{P_{s,x}(t + \delta t) - P_{s,x}(t)}{\delta t} \\ &= \kappa P_{s-1,x}(t) + (s+1) \lambda P_{s+1,x}(t) + s \rho P_{s,x-1}(t) + (x+1) \mu P_{s,x+1}(t) \\ &\quad - (\kappa + s \lambda + s \rho + x \mu) P_{s,x}(t). \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

In an analogous way a chemical master equation can be derived for any biochemical network [14] and thus forms the basis for our further computations. Stochastic processes that can be described by a master equation are generally called *jump processes* and provide a useful abstraction for the processes that we want to consider.

2.1.4 Jump Processes

Since particle counts never become negative, eq. (2.10) describes a Markov process in continuous time with the state space $\{(s, x) | s \in \mathbb{N}_0, x \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$. In general, every continuous-time Markov process with a discrete state space obeys a master equation. Such processes are also commonly called *jump processes* since they generate discontinuous sample paths [21].

A jump process with state space \mathcal{U} and an initial state $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathcal{U}$ at time t_0 generates trajectories that can be described by a sequence of pairs $(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i)_{i=1,2,\dots}$ where at every *transition time* t_i there occurs a jump in state space $\mathbf{x}_{i-1} \rightarrow \mathbf{x}_i$. As illustrated in eq. (2.10) the master equation encodes the transition rates for all possible state changes in the system. Similarly, for an arbitrary jump process we can formulate the master equation

$$\frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}_0, t_0)}{\partial t} = \sum_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{U}} [w_t(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') P(\mathbf{x}', t | \mathbf{x}_0, t_0) - w_t(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}) P(\mathbf{x}, t | \mathbf{x}_0, t_0)] \quad (2.11)$$

where $w_t(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x})$ specifies the rate for the transition $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{x}'$ at time t and $w_t(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) = 0$. The first term of the sum in eq. (2.11) is known as the *gain* since it describes how probability flows from other states into the current one while the second term is called *loss* as it expresses how much probability flows away from the current state. This form of the master equation allows us to find a relatively simple expression for the probability of individual trajectories of jump processes.

2.1.5 Probability Densities of Trajectories

From eqns. (2.3) and (2.4) we can see immediately that the computation of the mutual information between two random variables relies on the calculation of (conditional) probability densities for these variables. Our interest in this thesis lies in the computation of the mutual information for time-varying signals and responses. Hence, we need to evaluate the mutual information between random variables whose individual samples are *entire trajectories*. To do this we require the notion of probability for a given trajectory, based on a given biochemical model for a cell. In the following derivation we show how the master equation as formulated in eq. (2.11) makes it possible to compute the trajectory probability exactly for the corresponding reaction network. In the next chapter we will then discuss how to use these results in practice to compute the conditional probability of a response $P(\mathbf{x} | \mathbf{s})$ for trajectories \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{x} .

We define the probability of a trajectory with N jumps as the joint probability density of the sequence of states and transition times $P(\mathbf{x}_0, t_0; \dots; \mathbf{x}_N, t_N)$. We include the initial state \mathbf{x}_0, t_0 in the probability since the initial condition itself is usually given by a probability distribution. Using conditional probabilities we can write

$$P(\mathbf{x}_0, t_0; \dots; \mathbf{x}_N, t_N) = P(\mathbf{x}_0, t_0) P(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1 | \mathbf{x}_0, t_0) P(\mathbf{x}_2, t_2 | \mathbf{x}_1, t_1; \mathbf{x}_0, t_0) \cdots P(\mathbf{x}_N, t_N | \mathbf{x}_{N-1}, t_{N-1}; \dots; \mathbf{x}_0, t_0). \quad (2.12)$$

We can make use of the fact that jump processes are Markov processes to simplify eq. (2.12) such that every conditional probability only explicitly depends on the immediately preceding state

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{x}_0, t_0; \dots; \mathbf{x}_N, t_N) &= P(\mathbf{x}_0, t_0) P(\mathbf{x}_1, t_1 | \mathbf{x}_0, t_0) P(\mathbf{x}_2, t_2 | \mathbf{x}_1, t_1) \cdots P(\mathbf{x}_N, t_N | \mathbf{x}_{N-1}, t_{N-1}) \\ &= P(\mathbf{x}_0, t_0) \prod_{i=1}^N P(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i | \mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}). \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

Hence the expression for the probability of a trajectory contains two distinct kinds of probability distributions, a) the probability of the initial condition $P(\mathbf{x}_0, t_0)$ and b) the transition probabilities for every step in the trajectory given by $P(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i | \mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1})$. The initial condition $P(\mathbf{x}_0, t_0)$ depends on the specific problem and will often be taken to be the steady-state distribution. We will discuss this issue in more detail in sec. 3.3.3. For the transition probabilities however, we can find a simple expression in terms of the master equation.

The transition probability $P(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i | \mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1})$ describes the probability for a small segment of the trajectory from t_{i-1} to t_i where first, the system is at state \mathbf{x}_{i-1} for a duration $t_i - t_{i-1}$ and then makes a jump $\mathbf{x}_{i-1} \rightarrow \mathbf{x}_i$. We are now going to derive how to express the probabilities of the constant part as well as the probability of the jump using only terms from the master equation given in eq. (2.11). At the start of the segment, the probability for there to be no jump until at least $t > t_{i-1}$ is called the *survival probability* $S(\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}, t)$. By noticing that the change in the survival probability is given by the *loss* term of the master equation

$$S(\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}, t + \delta t) = S(\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}, t) \left[1 - \delta t \sum_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{U}} w_{t_{i-1}}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}_{i-1}) + \mathcal{O}(\delta t^2) \right] \quad (2.14)$$

we can motivate the differential equation

$$\frac{\partial S(\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}, t)}{\partial t} = -S(\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}, t) \sum_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{U}} w_{t_{i-1}}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}_{i-1}) \quad (2.15)$$

with the solution

$$S(\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}, t) = \exp \left(- \int_{t_{i-1}}^t dt' \sum_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{U}} w_{t'}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}_{i-1}) \right). \quad (2.16)$$

The expression $S(\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}, t)$ is the probability for no reaction happening from time t_{i-1} until *at least* t . The survival probability therefore is the cumulative probability distribution for the *waiting time* $\tau_{i-1} = t - t_{i-1}$, i.e. we can write $P(\tau_{i-1} \geq \delta) = S(\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}, t_{i-1} + \delta)$. Since the probability for the waiting time to be *exactly* $\tau_{i-1} = t_i - t_{i-1}$ is *zero* we instead compute the probability density

$$P(\tau_{i-1} = t_i - t_{i-1}) = \left. \frac{\partial P(\tau_{i-1} < \delta)}{\partial \delta} \right|_{\delta=t_i-t_{i-1}} = \left. \frac{\partial [1 - S(\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}, t_{i-1} + \delta)]}{\partial \delta} \right|_{\delta=t_i-t_{i-1}}. \quad (2.17)$$

The jump $\mathbf{x}_{i-1} \rightarrow \mathbf{x}_i$ at time t_i itself happens with probability

$$P(\mathbf{x}_{i-1} \rightarrow \mathbf{x}_i, t_i) = \frac{w_{t_i}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_{i-1})}{\sum_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{U}} w_{t_i}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}_{i-1})}. \quad (2.18)$$

Combining the jump probability with the survival probability we can thus express the transition probability density by the multiplication

$$P(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i | \mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}) = P(\tau_{i-1} = t_i - t_{i-1}) P(\mathbf{x}_{i-1} \rightarrow \mathbf{x}_i, t_i) \quad (2.19)$$

and by inserting the results from eqns. (2.16) to (2.18) we arrive at the expression

$$P(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i | \mathbf{x}_{i-1}, t_{i-1}) = w_{t_i}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_{i-1}) \exp \left(- \int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_i} dt' \sum_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{U}} w_{t'}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}_{i-1}) \right). \quad (2.20)$$

Therefore eq. (2.20) plugged into eq. (2.13) allows the exact computation of probability densities for arbitrary stochastic trajectories. The results were derived in enough generality such that time-dependent transition rates are explicitly allowed. We will see that the analytical expression for the probability of a stochastic trajectory is central for the estimation of the mutual information throughout this thesis. Eqns. (2.13) and (2.20) will be used to compute the conditional probability $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ for stochastically generated signal and response trajectories \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{x} . Furthermore, the survival probability and the jump probability introduced in this section form the basis of the *Stochastic Simulation Algorithm* that is introduced in the following subsection.

2.1.6 Generating Stochastic Trajectories for Jump Processes

One main ingredient for a computational recipe to calculate the mutual information is the formula for the probability of a trajectory, as derived in the previous section. Of equal importance is the correct generation of stochastic realizations for the biochemical model we intend to study. So far we showed how to model any biochemical network as a *jump process* through the formulation of the chemical master equation. In the previous section we were able to derive an equation for the probability of a trajectory using only terms from the master equation. Similarly, we can formulate the *stochastic simulation algorithm* which efficiently generates trajectories for any jump process with a known master equation. In the following we explain the variant named *direct Gillespie algorithm* after its inventor [16].

The direct Gillespie algorithm is an efficient and exact procedure to generate stochastic trajectories for jump processes. Starting from an initial state \mathbf{x}_0 at time t_0 it generates a trajectory $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{x}_0, t_0; \dots; \mathbf{x}_N, t_N)$ that is a realization of the corresponding stochastic process. Since the trajectories of a jump process are constant segments, separated by discontinuous jumps, at every point in time the system either remains unchanged or it performs an instantaneous jump. Therefore the algorithm works in two phases that are repeated over and over until a trajectory of the desired length is generated.

In the first phase we compute the stochastic waiting time τ until the next *event* occurs. Given that we are currently at time t_{i-1} and state \mathbf{x}_{i-1} , the probability for the waiting time being $\tau \geq t - t_{i-1}$ is given by the survival probability from eq. (2.16). By the inverse function method we can generate a correctly distributed waiting time τ using a random variate u that is uniformly distributed between 0 and 1 and then solving the equation

$$u = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_{i-1}+\tau} dt' \sum_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{U}} w_{t'}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}_{i-1})\right) \quad (2.21)$$

for τ . We then set $t_i = t_{i-1} + \tau$. For general transition rates $w_{t'}$, eq. (2.21) will have no analytical solution and it may be necessary to use approximate numerical integration techniques to solve for τ . If however the transition rates are time-independent for a given state we find the simple solution

$$\tau = -\frac{\ln(1-u)}{\sum_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{U}} w_{t_{i-1}}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}_{i-1})}. \quad (2.22)$$

After the first phase we already know the time of the next event. Therefore all that remains to do is to decide which reaction should happen. The probability for the individual jumps is given by eq. (2.18) and thus we can make a weighted choice between all reactions according to their probabilities. Using this choice we have found the next state \mathbf{x}_i and we have finished one step in the stochastic simulation.

Using both of these phases we can iteratively generate entire trajectories for any given jump process. The derivations in this section were done with enough generality to be applicable even to jump processes with time-varying transition rates.

2.2 A Simple Model of Gene Expression

In the course of this thesis we explore computational methods for the estimation of the mutual information in cellular reaction networks. To test and analyze our algorithms we perform computations for a very simple biochemical network for gene expression, consisting in merely four reactions and two species. It represents one of the simplest possible problems that a Monte-Carlo approach should be able to solve. Consequently, an estimation procedure that fails even on this simple model will almost certainly not provide satisfactory results for more complex networks. So on one hand we use a very simple biochemical network as a minimal system that an algorithm must be able to solve. On the other hand this model for gene expression has already been studied from an information theoretical point of view. Its simple structure allowed Tostevin and ten Wolde [15] to derive precise analytical approximations for the mutual information that we can use to test the results of our computational estimates against. In the following we describe the biochemical network and derive some useful analytical results.

We begin by specifying the 4 reactions that make up a simple model for gene expression

and note that it is the same network that was already used in eq. (2.6). It includes two species, S and X that represent the signal and the response, respectively. The signal dynamics are fully

described by the first two reactions, i.e. a birth-death process where signals are “born” stochastically with a constant rate κ and every signal particle has a constant decay rate of λ . The response dynamics are given by the other two reactions in eq. (2.23). Each signal particle can stochastically produce a response with rate ρ and every response itself decays with rate μ . The stochastic process that corresponds to the full reaction network under well-mixed conditions is described by a chemical master equation that we anticipatigly already derived for this network in eq. (2.10). While the stochastic formulation describes the full reaction dynamics (assuming the system is well-mixed) we can understand many of its properties from a deterministic description.

The average number of signal particles $s(t)$ is described by the deterministic rate equation

$$\partial_t s(t) = \kappa - \lambda s(t). \quad (2.24)$$

This ODE has a fixed point that represents the steady-state average of the signal $\bar{s} = \kappa/\lambda$. In a similar way we can deterministically describe the average number of response particles $x(t)$ using the ODE

$$\partial_t x(t) = \rho s(t) - \mu x(t). \quad (2.25)$$

Analogous to the signal we have a steady state average for the response $\bar{x} = \rho\bar{s}/\mu$. In this case, the deterministic equations are not only useful to derive steady-state averages but can also be used to understand *correlations* between the components of the system. If S_t is the stochastic count of signal particles at time t we call $C_{ss}(t, t') = \langle S_t S_{t'} \rangle$ the *autocorrelation function* of \mathcal{S} . Similarly we can also define correlation functions between the signal and the response, such as $C_{sx}(t, t') = \langle S_t X_{t'} \rangle$, where by X_t we denote the stochastic number of X molecules at time t . Thus, in total we have four different correlation functions C_{ss}, C_{sx}, C_{xs} , and C_{xx} . If we assume the system is in steady state, the correlation functions do only depend on the time-difference $t' - t$ such that we can write $C_{\alpha\beta}(t, t') = C_{\alpha\beta}(t' - t)$ [14]. For simple biochemical networks like eq. (2.23) it is relatively straightforward to analytically derive the correlation functions for the steady state.

Since the deterministic eqns. (2.24) and (2.25) are both *first-order* ODEs we say that the biochemical system has *linear equations of motions* such that for some matrix $A(t)$ and vector $\xi(t)$ we can write

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{z}(t)}{\partial t} = A(t) \mathbf{z}(t) + \xi(t) \quad (2.26)$$

with $\mathbf{z}(t) = (s(t), x(t))^T$. We say that the corresponding Markov process describes a *linear system*. In the following we make use of the fact that for linear systems we can apply the *regression*

theorem [14]

$$\partial_t C_{ij}(t) = - \sum_k A_{ik}(t) C_{kj}(t) \quad (2.27)$$

where C_{ij} are the correlation functions. Specifically, for our biochemical network we find the following set of coupled differential equations for the correlation functions

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t C_{ss}(t) &= -\lambda C_{ss}(t) \\ \partial_t C_{sx}(t) &= \rho C_{ss}(t) - \mu C_{sx}(t) \\ \partial_t C_{xs}(t) &= -\lambda C_{xs}(t) \\ \partial_t C_{xx}(t) &= \rho C_{xs}(t) - \mu C_{xx}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.28)$$

with the solutions for $t \geq 0$ (assuming steady-state initial conditions)

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ss}(t) &= \frac{\kappa}{\lambda} e^{-\lambda t} \\ C_{sx}(t) &= \frac{\rho\kappa}{\lambda(\lambda - \mu)} \left[\left(1 + \frac{\lambda - \mu}{\lambda + \mu}\right) e^{-\mu t} - e^{-\lambda t} \right] \\ C_{xs}(t) &= \frac{\rho\kappa}{\lambda(\lambda + \mu)} e^{-\lambda t} \\ C_{xx}(t) &= \frac{\rho^2\kappa}{\lambda(\lambda^2 - \mu^2)} (e^{-\mu t} - e^{-\lambda t}) + \left(1 + \frac{\rho}{\lambda + \mu}\right) \frac{\rho\kappa}{\lambda\mu} e^{-\mu t}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.29)$$

Since by definition $C_{\alpha\beta}(-t) = C_{\beta\alpha}(t)$, from eq. (2.29) we know the complete correlation functions for the system in steady state. The correlation functions are plotted in fig. 2.2 to visualize the system behavior.

The steady-state averages and the correlation functions represent the first and second moments of the trajectories of \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} . By discarding all higher-order moments and discretizing time we build an approximate stochastic model for the chemical reaction network that allows further analytic results. Since we will approximate the trajectories using samples from multivariate normal distributions, this method is often called the *Gaussian approximation*. For a given discretization $t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_d$ we describe the signal and response trajectories as a vector of values at discrete sample times. For simplicity the values are taken to be deviations from the average e.g. we discretize a signal as $\mathbf{s} = (s(t_1) - \bar{s}, \dots, s(t_d) - \bar{s})^T$. In the following we define a multivariate probability density $P(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})$ for the signal and response trajectories such that the resulting approximate system has identical correlation functions to the full biochemical network.

Figure 2.2: Correlation functions for the steady state $C_{\alpha\beta}$ from eq. (2.29), plotted as functions of time. They describe how the deviations from the mean correlate over time. The solid lines represent the autocorrelation functions whereas the dashed lines display correlations between the signal and response. The slight peak at $t' - t \approx 70$ of $C_{sx}(t' - t) = \langle S_t X_{t'} \rangle$ shows that the chemical interaction between S and X leads to positive correlations between them. For the reaction rates the values from tbl. 2.1 were used.

Hence we consider the case where the joint probability distribution $P(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})$ is given by a multivariate normal distribution

$$P(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^{2d} \det Z}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{s}^T \ \mathbf{x}^T) Z^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{s} \\ \mathbf{x} \end{pmatrix} \right] \quad (2.30)$$

where $\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ are the signal and response vectors respectively. The symmetric positive-definite covariance matrix $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{2d \times 2d}$ has the block form

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} C_{ss} & C_{xs} \\ C_{sx} & C_{xx} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.31)$$

with matrices $C_{\alpha\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$. The correlation functions in eq. (2.29) then give us the elements of the matrix blocks

$$(C_{\alpha\beta})_{ij} = C_{\alpha\beta}(t_j - t_i). \quad (2.32)$$

For the joint distribution in eq. (2.30) there exists a simple analytical expression to compute the mutual information between \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} [7,15]

$$I(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{X}) = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{\det C_{ss} \det C_{xx}}{\det Z} \right) \quad (2.33)$$

which will be our benchmark to compare the proposed Monte-Carlo estimation procedure against. In a similar way we can also acquire analytical equations for both the marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X})$ and the conditional entropy $H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S})$.

While we can use eq. (2.33) to directly evaluate the mutual information for trajectories using discretized time, Tostevin, et. al. [15] derive—specifically for this reaction network—a formula to analytically compute the mutual information rate (in nats per unit time) in the limit of infinitely fine discretization

$$I_R = \frac{\lambda}{2} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{\rho}{\lambda}} - 1 \right). \quad (2.34)$$

In this subsection we analyzed a simple, yet non-trivial example of a biochemical network for which we intend to compute the mutual information using Monte-Carlo techniques. Since we were able to derive the correlation functions for this network, we can make use of the Gaussian approximation to estimate the mutual information using eq. (2.33). That approximation will turn out to be very useful to understand the accuracy of Monte-Carlo estimates. To make the different results in this thesis comparable we used consistent parameter values for the reaction constants that are shown in tbl. 2.1.

Table 2.1: Values of the reaction constants along with the steady-state averages, correlation times and approximate information rate from eq. (2.34). The values for the reaction constants were used for all computations unless stated otherwise.

κ	λ	ρ	μ	\bar{s}	\bar{x}	τ_s	τ_x	I_R
0.25	0.005	0.01	0.01	50	50	200	180	0.00183

3 Monte Carlo Estimate of the Mutual Information

Equipped with analytical formulae for the computation of trajectory probabilities and with methods for efficient stochastic simulation, we can start to develop estimates for the mutual information. The basis for our method is eq. (2.4); specifically we separate the mutual information into two parts that are computed independently, the *marginal entropy* $H(\mathcal{X})$ and the *conditional entropy* $H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S})$. Since signals and responses are time-varying, both entropies involve integrals over spaces of trajectories which are high-dimensional. At high dimensionality, direct numerical integration is not viable and instead, we use Monte Carlo approaches based on random sampling of signals and responses.

While Monte Carlo methods comprise a wide variety of approaches to stochastically evaluate integrals or sums the common idea is easily stated. We have a state space U and a probability distribution p_U on that state space. The problem is to numerically evaluate integrals of the form

$$F = \langle f(u) \rangle = \int_U du p_U(u) f(u) \tag{3.1}$$

where $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is some function of interest. If U is high-dimensional it is very time-consuming to estimate it by direct numerical integration. Instead, we generate random samples u_1, u_2, \dots from the probability distribution p_U such that by the *law of large numbers* we have the equality

$$F = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N f(u_i)}{N} \tag{3.2}$$

i.e. the sample average of random samples converges towards their mean. In practice, we can't evaluate the limit in eq. (3.2) and we approximate F using a finite number N of random samples

$$\hat{F} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N f(u_i)}{N}. \tag{3.3}$$

In this chapter we will show how to use Monte Carlo integration to compute the mutual information between stochastic trajectories. The computation requires the estimation of two quantities, marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X})$ and the conditional entropy $H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S})$. We will show how to perform Monte Carlo estimates for both entropies, however as we will explain, the marginal entropy turns out to be computationally much more difficult to estimate.

3.1 Monte Carlo Estimate for the Marginal Entropy

We start by considering an abstract system, consisting of two random variables \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} representing the possible signals and responses, respectively. We will assume the availability of efficient computational methods to generate random samples from either of these random variables. In this subsection we show how to use Monte Carlo techniques to estimate the marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X})$ while in the following subsection we describe a similar method to estimate the conditional entropy $H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S})$.

We intend to compute the marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X})$ using Monte Carlo (MC) sampling to evaluate the necessary integrals. First, given a number of random samples $(\mathbf{x}_i)_{i=1,\dots,N_x}$ taken from \mathcal{X} we propose as an estimate for the entropy

$$H(\mathcal{X}) = - \int d\mathbf{x} P(\mathbf{x}) \ln P(\mathbf{x}) \approx - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_x} \ln P(\mathbf{x}_i)}{N_x}. \quad (3.4)$$

I.e. using numerous response samples, we compute the sample average of their individual log-probabilities $\ln P(\mathbf{x}_i)$. As explained in the following section, from a biochemical of a cell we are not able to directly compute $P(\mathbf{x}_i)$. We do however have an efficient way of *generating* the responses $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots$ using the stochastic simulation algorithm.

Nonetheless, we see from eq. (3.4) that we *do* have to evaluate $P(\mathbf{x}_i)$ for every generated sample. To solve this problem we choose to evaluate $P(\mathbf{x}_i)$ by doing another nested Monte Carlo integration using signal samples $(\mathbf{s}_j)_{j=1,\dots,N_s}$ from \mathcal{S} to write

$$P(\mathbf{x}_i) = \int d\mathbf{s} P(\mathbf{s}) P(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{s}) \approx \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_s} P(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{s}_j)}{N_s}. \quad (3.5)$$

Hence, for every response sample \mathbf{x}_i we have to perform a sample average over the conditional probabilities $P(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{s}_j)$. Again, anticipating results from the following section, we make use of the fact that a stochastic model for a biochemical network allows us to efficiently compute $P(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{s}_j)$. Therefore it seems viable to use eq. (3.5) to compute the marginal probability for a given response.

While for a low-dimensional signal space it is feasible to instead compute the marginalization integral eq. (3.5) using direct evaluation [20] we choose to use a nested MC simulation to also be able to handle high-dimensional signal spaces. This is crucial since time-varying signals are described by high-dimensional trajectories.

We can summarize the estimation procedure for the marginal entropy using the equation

$$H(\mathcal{X}) = - \left\langle \ln \langle P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) \rangle_{P(\mathbf{s})} \right\rangle_{P(\mathbf{x})} \quad (3.6)$$

where we use the notation $\langle f(x) \rangle_{g(x)}$ for the expected value of $f(x)$ when x is distributed according to the probability density given by $g(x)$. Thus when thinking in mathematical terms we have the shorthand $\langle f(x) \rangle_{g(x)} \equiv \int dx g(x)f(x)$. We can also easily translate this notation into a Monte Carlo estimate, i.e. $\langle f(x) \rangle_{g(x)} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N f(x_i)}{N}$ where x_1, x_2, \dots are independent samples of the probability distribution given by $g(x)$.

3.2 Estimating the Conditional Entropy

We can also estimate the *conditional entropy* using MC averages over trajectories. We express the conditional entropy using the notation introduced in eq. (3.6)

$$H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S}) = - \iint ds dx P(\mathbf{s})P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) \ln P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) = - \left\langle \left\langle \ln P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) \right\rangle_{P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})} \right\rangle_{P(\mathbf{s})} \quad (3.7)$$

to show that we require nested Monte Carlo integrations to evaluate the integral. We first generate signal samples $\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{N_s}$ from the density $P(\mathbf{s})$. Let $\mathbf{x}_i^1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_i^{N_x}$ be response samples generated from $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}_i)$. The Monte Carlo estimate for the conditional entropy then reads

$$H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S}) \approx - \frac{1}{N_s N_x} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_x} \ln P(\mathbf{x}_i^j|\mathbf{s}_i). \quad (3.8)$$

In this section and the previous section we have shown that using Monte Carlo computations we can in principle compute the mutual information between arbitrary random variables.

3.3 Monte Carlo Simulations for Trajectories

In the previous sections we have presented a Monte Carlo estimate for the mutual information (MI) $I(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{X})$ where \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} were considered to be abstract random variables. Now we are going to explain how we can do these estimates when \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} are actually random variables whose values are entire trajectories.

The main idea is to use the stochastic simulation algorithm (SSA) to generate stochastic realizations of \mathcal{X} from a given signal trajectory \mathbf{s} . In our case, the signals themselves are also realizations of a stochastic process. To allow for maximal generality we assume that we merely know that the stochastic dynamics of \mathcal{S} are given by a stochastic differential equation (SDE). Hence, we want to use the SDE to generate a set of signals and for every signal we can use the SSA to generate appropriate responses. Using the set of signals and responses we can perform the Monte Carlo estimate of the MI.

3.3.1 General Stochastic Dynamics of Signals

In the previous section we found that both, the Monte Carlo computation of the marginal entropy and of the conditional entropy require the generation of stochastic samples of the signal. This is not surprising since the stochastic dynamics of the signal reflect the amount of information that it contains. For example, if the signal is mostly governed by noise, then even the most efficient biochemical network could not extract a lot of meaningful information out of it. Therefore, to compute the mutual information between the signal and the responses, apart from modeling the biochemical network that processes the signal we also have to model the signal-generating process.

Generally, any kind of noisy signal can be modeled by a *stochastic process*. In many physically relevant cases, these processes arise as the solutions of SDEs that describe the underlying deterministic physics of the signal together with a *noise term* that gives rise to the stochastic nature of the signal trajectories. An example for such a process is the *Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process* that describes the random motion of a diffusing particle in a harmonic potential well [14]. It represents a combination of a deterministic harmonic oscillator together with fluctuations arising from the diffusion process. For the kinds of stochastic processes that are described by a SDE there exist many numerical methods to generate approximate signals trajectories. A simple, yet

effective method to generate stochastic realizations of SDEs is the *Euler–Maruyama method* that is a generalization of the Euler method for integrating ODEs [22]. Using such methods we can in principle choose any integrable SDE as the signal-generating process for the computation of the mutual information.

If we want to investigate the simple reaction network for gene expression given in eq. (2.23) we find that the signal dynamics are themselves described by a reaction network. In that case it is possible to generate *exact* stochastic realizations of signal trajectories using a stochastic simulation algorithm as discussed in sec. 2.1.6.

3.3.2 Generating Responses for Time-Varying Signals

Both, the estimate for the marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X})$ and the estimate for the conditional entropy $H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S})$ require the generation of appropriate responses to a given time-varying signal. To find stochastically correct responses for a given signal we have to understand how the biochemical network interacts with the signal. In many cases the signal itself is a molecular species that participates in the reaction network. In this scenario, an abundance of signal directly leads to an increased rate of all reactions in which the signal molecule acts as a reactant. In other cases the signal may be a thermodynamic quantity as for example the environmental temperature. Changes in temperature usually effect the rates of *all* reactions in a chemical reaction network. Thus, in general we think of a signal as a quantity whose value affects some or all of the reaction rates of the biochemical network at a given instant. Since we model the signal as a time-varying process, for a given realization of the signal we can describe the corresponding responses using a master equation with time-dependent reaction rates.

We describe the coupling of the biochemical network to the signal through an explicit dependence of the reaction rates from eq. (2.11) on the signal level $s(t)$. Thus we write the master equation for the responses as

$$\frac{\partial P(x, t|x_0, t_0, \mathbf{s})}{\partial t} = \sum_{x' \in \mathcal{U}} [w_t(x, x', s(t)) P(x', t|x_0, t_0, \mathbf{s}) - w_t(x', x, s(t)) P(x, t|x_0, t_0, \mathbf{s})] \quad (3.9)$$

which shows the explicit dependence of the stochastic dynamics on the given signal trajectory \mathbf{s} . Since we assume that the reaction rates are the *only* way in which the signal trajectory affects the

response we conclude that stochastic realizations of the process described by eq. (3.9) are distributed according to the conditional distribution $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$. In agreement with standard terminology we call $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ the likelihood of \mathbf{x} with respect to \mathbf{s} .

The formulation of the master equation with an explicit dependence on the signals makes it possible to perform the Monte Carlo estimates as described above. Specifically, by making use of results derived in the previous chapter we can perform three crucial operations needed for the computational estimate of the mutual information.

Generation of response trajectories according to $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$

As already described above, for any signal trajectory \mathbf{s} we can formulate the master equation as written in eq. (3.9) and use the stochastic simulation algorithm for time-dependent reaction rates to generate correctly distributed response trajectories.

Generation of response trajectories according to $P(\mathbf{x})$

Similarly we can generate independent draws from the distribution $P(\mathbf{x})$ by first generating a stochastic realization \mathbf{s} of the signal from the corresponding stochastic process and then generating exactly one response according to $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$.

Computation of $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$

Finally, for any signal-response pair of trajectories, we can compute the conditional probability $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ using the formulae for the trajectory probability derived before in eqns. (2.13) and (2.20) and inserting the reaction rates for the given signal trajectory \mathbf{s} .

3.3.3 Probability Distribution of the Initial State

We have shown that we can use the stochastic simulation algorithm (SSA) to simulate response trajectories for a given signal. Note however, that the SSA needs us to specify the initial copy numbers of all species in the biochemical network. From this initial state we can then evolve the stochastic dynamics of the reactions in time. Hence, we have to think about the correct

Figure 3.1: Monte Carlo computation of the probability $p_{X|S}(x_0|s_0)$. If t_0 is the present, we start by generating a signal trajectory into the future. From its initial point we then generate N_{past} trajectories backwards in time. For every one of these past signals we simulate a corresponding response trajectory as shown in the lower part of the figure. From the intersection of the responses with t_0 we compute the probability distribution using a Gaussian kernel density estimate.

choice of the initial condition. In some cases it might be reasonable to have the same predefined initial condition for all responses that are simulated, e.g. in the beginning there is no response $x(t_0) = 0$. In many cases however, the initial states x_0 will be distributed according to some probability density $P(x_0, t_0)$. A common example are systems that start out in a *steady state*, i.e. at t_0 both the signal and the response are distributed according to their joint stationary distribution $p_{S,X}(s, x)$.

In that case, to set up the initial conditions correctly, we start by generating one signal trajectory whose initial point s_0 is drawn from the signal's stationary distribution $p_S(s_0)$. Thus, to ensure that the initial condition is drawn from $p_{S,X}(s, x)$, we need to pick the initial condition of the response x_0 from the conditional distribution $p_{X|S}(x_0|s_0)$. For our simulations, we estimate that conditional distribution in a separate computation for every signal that is generated.

If the signal dynamics in steady state are time-reversible, we can estimate the distribution function $p_{X|S}(x_0|s_0)$ for a given s_0 by generating time-reversed signal trajectories. The idea is to generate N_{past} signal trajectories of duration t_{past} , *backwards in time*, starting from s_0 at time t_0 that represent possible “pasts” of the system. For every such trajectory we then generate a re-

sponse trajectory of the same duration *forward in time*. That is, the response starts at time $t_0 - t_{\text{past}}$ with some arbitrary initial state x_{past} and continues until time t_0 . Since we generate N_{past} signals into the past, we end up with N_{past} response trajectories, whose end points at t_0 are distributed according to $p_{X|S}(x_0|s_0)$.

From these points $x_0^{(1)}, \dots, x_0^{(N_{\text{past}})}$ we estimate the distribution function $p_{X|S}(x_0|s_0)$ using Gaussian kernel density estimation (KDE) [23,24]. The KDE yields a smooth estimate of the conditional distribution $p_{X|S}(x_0|s_0)$ from the sample points. This estimated distribution is used in two different ways, a) to sample the starting point for the generated response and b) to compute the probability of the initial point $P(\mathbf{x}_0, t_0)$ which appears in the expression of the trajectory probability given in eq. (2.13).

In summary, as long as we can formulate a stochastic process that describes the signal dynamics *and* we understand how the signal level affects the reaction rates of the biochemical network, we can in principle use the Monte Carlo procedure described in the previous section to estimate the mutual information. From the signal's SDE we generate stochastic realizations using appropriate numerical integrators for SDEs such as the *Euler–Maruyama method* or the *stochastic simulation algorithm*. For every signal realization we have shown how to use the SSA to generate corresponding response trajectories. In the following section we will use these methods on a simple model of gene expression to see how the method is implemented in practice.

3.4 Returning to the Simple Model of Gene Expression

To evaluate the estimation procedure described so far in this chapter, we used it to compute the mutual information for the simple biochemical network introduced in sec. 2.2. As the initial condition we assumed that the system is in the steady state such that we were able to compare our Monte Carlo estimates with the analytical results from eq. (2.33). We generated all signals and responses using a stochastic simulation algorithm (SSA) for the reaction network in eq. (2.23). The reaction rates were chosen as specified in tbl. 2.1 and the computed mutual information is always presented in units of *nats*, where $1 \text{ nat} = (1/\ln 2) \text{ bits}$.

3.4.1 Simulating Signals and Responses

In the model, the signal dynamics arise from the reactions $\emptyset \xrightarrow{\kappa} S, S \xrightarrow{\lambda} \emptyset$ that describe a simple birth-death process. Therefore, to generate signal trajectories we used the SSA with the initial copy numbers distributed according to the stationary distribution [14]

$$P_S(s_0) = e^{-\kappa/\lambda} \frac{(\kappa/\lambda)^{s_0}}{s_0!} \quad (3.10)$$

for $s_0 \in \mathbb{N}_0$. The trajectories generated by the SSA consist of piecewise constant segments in between the transition times $t_0 < \dots < t_N$. We can thus describe a trajectory \mathbf{s} as a function $s : [t_0, t_N] \rightarrow \mathbb{N}_0$ given by

$$s(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} s_i \theta(t - t_i) \theta(t_{i+1} - t) \quad (3.11)$$

where s_1, \dots, s_{N-1} are the sequence of copy numbers of S and θ is the Heaviside function. When we generate response trajectories corresponding to a given signal trajectory, the transition rate $w_t(x+1, x)$ for the reaction $S \xrightarrow{\rho} S + X$ is proportional to the function in eq. (3.11), i.e.

$$w_t(x+1, x) = \rho s(t). \quad (3.12)$$

Eq. (3.12) thus precisely specifies how a given signal trajectory interacts with the response. We use eqns. (2.21), (3.11) and (3.12) to compute the stochastic waiting times inside the SSA for the response trajectories.

To use the SSA for the generation of response trajectories, we need to solve eq. (2.21) which includes performing a time integral of the transition rates. The expression in eq. (3.11) allows us to integrate a signal trajectory with respect to time to arrive at

$$\int_{t_0}^t d\tau s(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} s_i [(t - t_i) \theta(t - t_i) - (t - t_{i+1}) \theta(t - t_{i+1})] \quad (3.13)$$

which naturally is a piecewise linear function of t . Using eq. (3.13) it is then straightforward to solve eq. (2.21) for u and use the SSA as described in sec. 2.1.6 to generate response trajectories. For response trajectories, we set the initial copy number x_0 of X according to the empirically generated distribution $P(x_0|s_0)$.

Similarly, for the computation of the likelihood $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ we use eqns. (2.13) and (2.20) which also depend on time integrals of transition rates. Hence using the results in this section, we can

generate stochastic realizations of signal trajectories and corresponding response trajectories. In other words, we can draw samples from the distributions $P(\mathbf{s})$ and $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ which we will use to estimate the mutual information.

3.4.2 Consistent Bias in Comparisons with Analytic Approximations

The Monte Carlo estimate of the mutual information (MI) was performed using two independent computations, a) an average over the *likelihoods* $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ of random responses with respect to their corresponding signals in eq. (3.8) that yields the conditional entropy and b) an average over the *marginal probability densities* $P(\mathbf{x})$ of sampled responses in eq. (3.4) for the marginal entropy. The difference of these two quantities is our estimate of the MI $I(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{X}) = H(\mathcal{X}) - H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S})$.

It is crucial to note that the two independent computations involved in the MI are not of equal difficulty. The evaluation of $P(\mathbf{x})$ requires a nested Monte Carlo simulation eq. (3.5) for every generated response. The inner computation of $P(\mathbf{x})$ can suffer especially high Monte Carlo variance since in eq. (3.5) the sampling distribution $P(\mathbf{s})$ may have only very little overlap with the integrand $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$. Specifically, it might be the case that most of the generated signals $\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{N_S} \sim P(\mathcal{S})$ contribute very weakly to the integral since their likelihoods $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}_i) \approx 0$ for almost all i . Consequently, only a very small number of signals may actually determine the estimate of $P(\mathbf{x})$ which leads to a high variance of the estimate. In conclusion, we expect the marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X})$ to be more difficult to estimate than the conditional entropy $H(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{S})$. This expectation is confirmed by the results in this chapter.

In order to understand how the inner Monte Carlo computation of $P(\mathbf{x})$ influences the estimate of the MI we performed an array of simulations with different values of N_S . The number N_S specifies how many signals we generate for every nested Monte Carlo computation of $P(\mathbf{x})$. We expect that increasing N_S leads to a better estimate of the marginal density for every response and therefore improves the estimate of the MI. We compare the simulation results with a reference value for the MI that was obtained by a Gaussian approximation. Using eq. (2.33) we can analytically compute the MI $I(\mathcal{S}_T, \mathcal{X}_T)$ between trajectories of duration T and using eq. (2.34) the information rate I_R between \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} . The analytically obtained values for the MI and the information rate are shown as red dotted lines in figs. 3.2 and 3.3. From a single simulation of the MI with a trajectory duration of T_{\max} we can similarly compute the MI $I(\mathcal{S}_T, \mathcal{X}_T)$ for any $T \in [0, T_{\max}]$ by simply

Figure 3.2: Estimates of the mutual information $I(\mathcal{S}_T, \mathcal{X}_T)$ for varying trajectory duration T . Every line shows an estimate of $I(\mathcal{S}_T, \mathcal{X}_T) = H(\mathcal{X}_T) - H(\mathcal{X}_T|\mathcal{S}_T)$ where the marginal and the conditional entropy were computed in separate simulations. For the marginal entropy we generated 2×10^5 independent responses per simulation and for every response \mathbf{x} computed the marginal density $P(\mathbf{x})$ using N_S signal trajectories. Hence, this figure shows how the nested estimate of the marginal density influences the overall result. While increasing N_S helps, all simulations consistently over-estimate the mutual information when compared to the analytic reference result computed using eq. (2.33). The estimation error appears to increase linearly with trajectory length and therefore leads to a biased estimate of the information rate. For the conditional entropy we generated 2×10^5 signals trajectories and for every signal we generated 10^3 response trajectories for the Monte Carlo average in eq. (3.8).

truncating all trajectories to duration T . An estimate for the information rate can be obtained by approximating the limit in eq. (2.34)

$$\hat{I}_R = \frac{I(\mathcal{S}_{T_{\max}}, \mathcal{X}_{T_{\max}})}{T_{\max}} \quad (3.14)$$

assuming $T_{\max} \gg \tau$ where τ is the longest timescale in the system.

In fig. 3.2 we show the the results of the different simulations to compute the MI between trajectories of varying durations T . We start by describing the features that all simulations have in common. In all cases we see a linear increase of the mutual information with trajectory length. The linearity is to be expected for trajectory durations $T \gg \tau$ where τ is the correlation time of

Figure 3.3: Estimated information rate $I_R = I(\mathcal{S}_T, \mathcal{X}_T)/T$ from the same data that was used in fig. 3.2. The reference line represents the analytical result $I_R = 0.00183$ from eq. (2.34). For a correct Monte Carlo simulation we expect the estimated information rate to converge towards the reference line as $T \rightarrow \infty$. However, while we see that the estimates converge towards a stable value for large T , all simulations considerably over-estimate the information rate. Even though for increasing N_S the estimates *do* improve we can not acquire reasonable results for the simulations shown.

the system [15]. If the signal is much longer than the correlation time of the system it is impossible for any future response to still gain information about the beginning of the signal. Hence, for short trajectories, the increase in MI per unit time may be smaller than the asymptotic information rate since the signal has not yet reached the maximal integration length of the system. Thus, while there exist situations where for small T the MI increases faster than linear, analytic computations using the Gaussian approximation confirm a fully linear increase of the MI from the start for the simple reaction network under consideration. In fig. 3.2, we show the result of eq. (2.33) for the Gaussian approximation as the dotted “reference” line.

For trajectory length $T = 0$ fig. 3.2 shows that all estimates—including the analytical result—coincide at a small non-zero value for their mutual information. This value is the mutual information between the initial conditions of the signal and the response. The agreement of all simulations shows that using the approach detailed in sec. 3.3.3 we were able correctly estimate the conditional distribution $P(x_0|s_0)$. For every response needed during our simulations we first generated 1000 signals backwards in time for $T_{\text{past}} = 500$ to choose a correct starting point for the response and to correctly compute the likelihood $P(x_0|s_0)$ of the initial condition.

Figure 3.4: Estimated information rate $I_R = I(S_T, \mathcal{X}_T)/T$ for three estimate with very large N_S . The reference line represents the analytical result $I_R = 0.00183$ from eq. (2.34). This plot highlights that even strong increases of N_S beyond 10^3 do not yield accurate results for the information rate. Our conclusion from this is that the simple Monte Carlo approach is too naïve and we have to find another way to improve accuracy, instead of spending more CPU time.

Thus, we see from fig. 3.2 that the estimated MI grows linearly with T and that all estimates agree on the MI for $T = 0$. However, we also find that each of the MI curves has a different slope. All Monte Carlo simulations significantly over-estimate the slope of the analytical reference line. As N_S increases we see a slight decrease of the MI slope, however even for largest simulation with $N_S = 1000$ the slope differs by more than 50% from the analytical reference. Further increasing N_S seems to yield diminishing returns. Hence, from the simulations we can't seem to accurately compute the information rate since it strongly depends on estimating the MI slopes correctly.

Asymptotically for $T \rightarrow \infty$ the slope of the MI with respect to the trajectory duration T converges towards the information rate I_R . In fig. 3.3 we see that all simulations show the convergence of the estimated information rate $I_R \approx I(S_T, \mathcal{X}_T)/T$ to a stable value already at $T \approx 150$. We again find that we over-estimate the information rate for simulations with $N_S \in \{10, 20, \dots, 1000\}$ even though we see slight improvement for larger N_S . We propose that even further increasing N_S and thus spending more CPU time per simulation is not worthwhile to improve the estimates.

To support that claim, in fig. 3.4 we show the results of two additional simulation with very high N_S and compare them to the analytical reference and the MI for $N_S = 1000$. Even for these very resource-intensive simulations we don't get better approximations for the information rate than for $N_S = 1000$. From these results we conclude that our approach is plagued by some

more fundamental problem that needs to be solved with other means than merely using more computational resources.

While we expect the main culprit to be the nested Monte Carlo estimates of the marginal density $P(\mathbf{x})$, it is difficult to obtain convincing evidence for that claim using the results shown so far. For an individual response trajectory \mathbf{x} we don't have a way to judge the accuracy of our estimate of $P(\mathbf{x})$. The only analytical result that we can use to check our results is the MI from the Gaussian approximation which is shown as the reference line in figs. 3.2 to 3.4. Therefore we decided to use the same Monte Carlo procedure to compute the MI with a simpler stochastic description of the signal and response trajectories which allows us to analytically validate all intermediate results. Thus, instead of using the SSA to fully simulate the signal and response dynamics we make the Gaussian approximation as introduced in sec. 2.2. Using that approximation, generating a signal or response amounts to taking a draw from a multivariate normal distributions with known covariance matrix.

3.5 Gaussian Approximation

Clearly, there is an issue with the computation of the mutual information (MI) for trajectories that prevents the accurate estimation using the simple Monte Carlo strategy shown above. In figs. 3.2 to 3.4 we saw that we consistently over-estimate the information rate regardless of the amount of computing time that was invested. To allow a deeper analysis of the underlying issue we repeated the estimates of the MI using a simpler, Gaussian model for signals and responses. Instead of simulating trajectories exactly in continuous time using the SSA, we choose a small time-interval Δt which we use to discretize the system. Conversely, while the SSA simulates individual reactions that lead to a discrete jumps in the trajectories, in the Gaussian approximation the copy numbers are approximated by continuous variables. Hence, we switch from a *discrete states and continuous time* description to a *continuous states and discrete time* approximation of the biochemical network.

3.5.1 Time Discretization

We discretize the time axis using a set of equidistant points $t_n = n\Delta t$ for $n = 1, \dots, d$. A signal trajectory is described a d -dimensional vector $\mathbf{s} = (s(t_1), \dots, s(t_d))^T$ where $s(t_i)$ describes

the deviation of the signal from its mean value \bar{s} at time t_i . The null vector therefore represents a trajectory that remains constant at \bar{s} for its entire duration whereas a non-zero vector indicates fluctuations. The Gaussian approximation for a biochemical network uses the correlation functions to derive a multivariate normal distribution such that the discretized system dynamics approximate the true stochastic dynamics of the network. Given a time-discretization we can use eq. (2.32) compute the covariance matrices $C_{ss}, C_{sx}, C_{xs}, C_{xx}$ from the correlation functions in eq. (2.29). From these covariance matrices we can derive all stochastic properties of the Gaussian approximation.

The signal dynamics are given by the probability distribution

$$P(\mathbf{s}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^d \det C_{ss}}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{s}^T C_{ss}^{-1} \mathbf{s}\right], \quad (3.15)$$

and similarly the response dynamics are determined by the marginal distribution

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^d \det C_{xx}}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{x}^T C_{xx}^{-1} \mathbf{x}\right]. \quad (3.16)$$

Notably, eq. (3.16) allows us to analytically compute the marginal density $P(\mathbf{x})$ without performing a Monte Carlo estimate of the integral $\int d\mathbf{s} P(\mathbf{s}) P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$. The joint distribution of \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} is given in eq. (2.30) which is a $2d$ -dimensional multivariate normal density function with covariance matrix

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} C_{ss} & C_{xs} \\ C_{sx} & C_{xx} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.17)$$

The conditional probability or likelihood $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ can be computed using the definition of the conditional probability $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) = P(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})/P(\mathbf{s})$.

Using this discretization we have two parameters left to tune. We can freely choose the number d and offsets Δt of our time samples. The duration of the trajectories \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{x} is given by the product $T = d\Delta t$. In fig. 3.5 we show matrix plots of the joint covariance matrix Z for different values of d and Δt . We can also observe that d determines the dimensionality of the problem while the product $d\Delta t$ serves as a measure for the sparsity of the correlation matrices.

Note that the choice of Δt affects how well the discretized trajectories approximate physical continuous-time trajectories. Thus, usually we would have to choose Δt to be relatively small such that the discretized process has similar dynamics compared to the continuous Gaussian process. For our purposes, this consideration is of secondary importance. We are merely comparing

Figure 3.5: Matrix plots of the full correlation matrix Z from eq. (3.17) for different values of dimensionality d and Δt . Brighter colors indicate higher matrix element values. We can clearly observe the block structure of Z in every matrix plot. For every matrix plot, the element with coordinates (i, j) in the top left quadrant shows the correlations $\langle s(i\Delta t)s(j\Delta t) \rangle$. In the top right quadrant we see the correlations $\langle s(i\Delta t)x(j\Delta t) \rangle$ and in the lower quadrants we see $\langle x(i\Delta t)s(j\Delta t) \rangle$ and $\langle x(i\Delta t)x(j\Delta t) \rangle$ on the left and right side respectively. The product $T = d\Delta t$ is the duration of the signal and response trajectories. The quantity $d\Delta t$ also serves as a rough measure of the sparsity of the correlation matrices (i.e. the fraction of matrix elements lower than some cutoff). Along diagonals from bottom left to top right, the product $T = d\Delta t$ is constant. Indeed, we see that along these diagonals the sparsity is roughly constant. Yet, as we move along such a diagonal of equal sparsity $d\Delta t$ but increasing dimensionality d we see correlation matrices that display the same features in a gradually more refined and smooth way.

the Monte Carlo estimates for the mutual information to the analytic results, obtained by computing the determinants of the covariance matrices. For a consistent Monte Carlo procedure we should expect convergence of the estimates to the analytic results given enough computing time. That is, while the choices of d and Δt should not affect the correctness of our procedure, it very well may strongly affect the computational resources needed for efficient estimation.

3.5.2 Direct Importance Sampling

We want to use this fully Gaussian model to understand how the sample sizes of the different Monte Carlo steps affect the estimate and whether there exists a bias in the approximation. We calculate the marginal entropy as a Monte Carlo average over the logarithms of the marginal distribution densities of N_x sampled responses as shown in eq. (3.4). The evaluation of the marginal density itself requires a Monte Carlo average over N_s sampled signals (eq. (3.5)). Hence to evaluate the marginal density we need to perform nested averaging as shown in eq. (3.6). We performed this procedure for various values of N_s and N_x and compared the estimate with reference results using the analytical expression for the entropy of a multivariate Gaussian distribution.

Both, increase of N_x and increase of N_s should lead to an improved estimate of $H(\mathcal{X})$. To understand the accuracy of an estimate with a given N_s and N_x we repeat the estimation procedure multiple times and compute the mean and the standard deviation of the individual estimation results.

In fig. 3.6 we see how the relative error of our estimate varies with the number of simulated responses N_x . Here use the same number of signals per response N_s for all estimates. While—as expected—the variance of the estimate decreases when we increase N_x we find that especially for very sparse covariance matrices we consistently over-estimate the marginal entropy. Indeed, we find that the systematic bias in our results seems to be independent of N_x .

We found that the bias is stronger for correlation matrices with higher sparsities $d\Delta t$. Since the sparsity grows with trajectory duration we can expect an increasingly strong over-estimation for longer trajectories. The sparsity can be increased either by decreasing the time-resolution or by increasing the dimensions of the covariance matrix. To understand how these parameters relate to each other we tested how the estimation error changes when we increase the dimensionality of the correlation matrices while the sparsity remains constant.

Figure 3.6: Top: relative error for the marginal entropy as a function of $1/N_x$. Bottom: empirical variance of ensembles of 144 estimates. The solid lines show a linear extrapolation of the data points for $N_x \rightarrow \infty$. All estimates were performed using a constant number of signal samples $N_s = 400$ and for $d = 200$. The linear extrapolation in the bottom plot indicates that we do predict the variance of the results to vanish in the limit of infinite sampling. This behavior is generally expected for Monte Carlo estimates. Strikingly however, we find that there is a consistent offset of the average estimate from the correct result, even in the limit $N_x \rightarrow \infty$. We see that the bias scales with the sparsity of the covariance matrices. The relative error is computed using $H_{\text{estimate}}/H_{\text{analytical}} - 1$ where $H_{\text{estimate}} = \sum_{i=1}^M \hat{H}_i/M$ is the average over the results of the $M = 144$ marginal entropy estimates that were performed using eq. (3.6) and $H_{\text{analytical}}$ is the value resulting from an analytical computation of the marginal entropy. The empirical variance shown is $\sum_{i=1}^M (\hat{H}_i - H_{\text{estimate}})^2/M$.

Figure 3.7: Absolute error of marginal entropy estimates for different values of the sparsity $d\Delta t$ of the correlation matrices. We see that for high dimensionality the lines of constant sparsity become increasingly flat. This indicates that for high-dimensional systems the sparsity of the covariance matrix is a good measure for the difficulty of correct estimation. We therefore claim that the bias of the entropy estimate for the Gaussian system primarily depends on the sparsity of the covariance matrix. Note that for lower numbers of dimensions the covariance matrices of along the diagonals of equal sparsity look more blocky (see fig. 3.5). That may be an indicator why the estimation error is not constant for a given sparsity at lower dimensions.

Fig. 3.7 shows how large the estimation error for the marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X})$ is on average for different levels of sparsity. We see that in all cases that increasing the sparsity leads to larger errors in the estimates. Additionally we find that for a given sparsity value, the estimates with high-dimensional covariance matrices are slightly worse. As we keep increasing the number of dimensions d at constant sparsity $d\Delta t$, thus decreasing Δt , the matrices gradually become a more faithful representation of the continuous correlation functions of the system (see fig. 3.5). Extrapolating the lines in fig. 3.7 we project that for very large covariance matrices, the sparsity is the only determining factor of the estimation bias.

As a next step we investigated how changes in the sampling for the marginal density $P(\mathbf{x}_i)$ affect the estimation bias. Thus in fig. 3.8 we show how the increase of simulated signals per response N_s improves the estimate of the marginal entropy. Here we again see that for high number of dimensions we over-estimate the marginal entropy. An increase of N_s does lead to slightly less over-estimation but the linear extrapolation indicates that even if we choose enormously high values for N_s we can not expect to reduce the bias substantially.

Figure 3.8: Relative error $H_{\text{estimate}}/H_{\text{analytical}} - 1$ as a function of $1/N_s$. We can see that the relative error in the marginal entropy estimate increases with the sparsity $d\Delta t$ (i.e. with trajectory duration). The linear extrapolating lines emphasize that there is a noticeable but very slight decrease in error as $N_s \rightarrow \infty$. This seems puzzling since for infinite sampling we should expect the error to vanish. Apparently for high-sparsity covariance matrices we need extraordinarily many signal samples to achieve unbiased estimates.

For a given number of samples, the fraction of the trajectory space probed by the Monte Carlo scheme is lower for longer durations. Therefore, for a given number of Monte Carlo samples we expect the estimate to become worse for longer trajectories, i.e. when the sparsity of the covariance matrix is high. This is confirmed by our results. Furthermore and in agreement with previous results we find that we consistently over-estimate the marginal entropy and while increasing N_s *does* reduce the bias slightly it appears to require an astronomically high sampling in signal trajectory space to reach arbitrary low errors. An increase in N_x however reduces the variance of the results but does not influence the bias at all.

Thus we are lead to believe that the main difficulty in estimating the marginal entropy is the Monte Carlo marginalization of the probability density function. To estimate $P(\mathbf{x})$ we sample signals from the marginal distribution $P(\mathbf{s})$ and average over the likelihoods $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$. However as the space of signals becomes increasingly vast for longer trajectories, it becomes more and more unlikely to sample a signal \mathbf{s} where \mathbf{x} has a non-vanishing likelihood of occurring. Hence the duration of the trajectories strongly influences the bias of the marginal entropy computation and we are well advised to keep the trajectories as short as possible. To capture the essential system dynamics however, the trajectories must be at least as long as the longest timescale τ in the system. If we are

interested in the marginal entropy for timescales longer than the longest timescale in the system we can then use the fact that trajectory pieces of duration $> \tau$ become independent of each other and we can add the individual entropies of these pieces to get the full entropy for such a long trajectory. For example, if we were interested in the marginal entropy of trajectories of duration $T = \ell\tau$ where $\ell \in \mathbb{N}^+$ we could approximate it by estimating the entropy \hat{H}_τ of trajectories of duration τ and then take $\ell\hat{H}_\tau$ as an approximation for $\hat{H}_{\ell\tau}$. While performing the estimate \hat{H}_τ is computationally much cheaper than directly estimating $\hat{H}_{\ell\tau}$ and therefore for a given amount of CPU-time we get a lower systematic bias of the estimate \hat{H}_τ , the bias of $\ell\hat{H}_\tau$ of course still scales linearly with ℓ . Therefore it is still in our best interest to reduce the systematic bias of the marginal entropy as much as possible.

3.5.3 Umbrella Sampling

To get a better estimate of $P(\mathbf{x})$ we decided to use *umbrella sampling*, i.e. to bias our sampling strategy towards signals that we expect to have a high likelihood for the given response. Since Monte Carlo estimates depend on the distribution of the chosen samples we must correct our estimate by re-weighting the samples accordingly.

More specifically, given a sampling distribution $w(\mathbf{s})$ (which is normalized like a probability density function) we can write

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = \int d\mathbf{s} w(\mathbf{s}) \frac{P(\mathbf{s})P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})}{w(\mathbf{s})} = \left\langle \frac{P(\mathbf{s})P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})}{w(\mathbf{s})} \right\rangle_{w(\mathbf{s})} \quad (3.18)$$

which shows us how to compute $P(\mathbf{x}_i)$ from signal trajectories $\mathbf{s}_1^w, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{N_s}^w$ which are distributed according to the sampling distribution given by w :

$$P(\mathbf{x}_i) \approx \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} \frac{P(\mathbf{s}_j^w)P(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{s}_j^w)}{w(\mathbf{s}_j^w)} \equiv P_{\mathbf{x}_i, N_s}^w. \quad (3.19)$$

The choice of the sampling distribution w has a direct impact on the variance of an ensemble of estimates $P_{\mathbf{x}_i, N_s}^w$. Indeed, for any given \mathbf{x}_i there is an optimal choice for the sampling distribution w_{opt} such that the variance of the estimates vanishes. This optimal choice is given by $w_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{s}) = P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}_i)$ which is easily confirmed by the calculation

$$P_{\mathbf{x}_i, N_s}^{w_{\text{opt}}} = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} \frac{P(\mathbf{s}_j^w)P(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{s}_j^w)}{P(\mathbf{s}_j^w|\mathbf{x}_i)} = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} P(\mathbf{x}_i) \quad (3.20)$$

Figure 3.9: Relative error as a function of the dimensionality d . The solid lines show the results using non-optimized sampling while the dashed lines show the results when using a sampling distribution close to the optimal distribution $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})$. We see that with optimized sampling there is no consistent over-estimation anymore. All estimated were done using $d = 200$ dimensional covariance matrices.

where in the last step we applied Bayes' rule. Since the expression above is completely independent of the chosen signal samples the result is deterministic and thus has zero variance. We also see from eq. (3.20) that in practice we can't directly use $w_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{s}) = P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}_i)$ as our sampling distribution since the evaluation of $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}_i) = \frac{P(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{s})P(\mathbf{s})}{P(\mathbf{x}_i)}$ itself depends on $P(\mathbf{x}_i)$ which is precisely the quantity we are interested in estimating.

Instead, we can try to obtain a sampling distribution that is as close as possible to $w_{\text{opt}}(\mathbf{s})$. A known approach involves using random samples from $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}_i)$ to pick the most optimal sampling distribution from a family of candidate distributions [25]. Generating so-called *posterior samples* from $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}_i) \sim P(\mathbf{x}_i|\mathbf{s})P(\mathbf{s})$ is generally possible without knowledge of the normalization factor $P(\mathbf{x}_i)$ e.g. by using Metropolis-Sampling [26,27]. To test within the Gaussian framework whether such an approach to importance sampling could work in principle, we generate 400 posterior samples by directly sampling from the analytically known posterior distribution $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}_i)$. We compute the empirical mean $\bar{\mathbf{s}}$ and the empirical covariance $\bar{\mathbf{C}}_{\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}_i}$ of these samples as parameter estimates for a multivariate Gaussian $\mathcal{N}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}_{\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}_i})$ and use the latter as an optimized sampling distribution.

In fig. 3.9 we show that using optimized sampling we can strongly reduce the systematic bias in

Figure 3.10: Comparison of the relative error of conditional entropy estimates versus marginal error estimates. The relative errors are shown on a logarithmic scale as a function of the sparsity. We can see that the relative error for the estimate of the conditional entropy is a few orders of magnitude smaller than the estimates of the marginal entropy. All estimates were performed with $N_x = 25600$ and $N_s = 1000$.

marginal entropy estimation. As expected, importance sampling is especially useful when the sparsity is very high, i.e. the trajectories are long. It is clear that for longer trajectories we expect $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}_i)$ to be a much more narrow sampling distribution than $P(\mathbf{s})$ whenever the \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} are not completely independent. Consequently, it becomes more and more unlikely to obtain a sample \mathbf{s}' from $P(\mathbf{s})$ such that $P(\mathbf{s}'|\mathbf{x}_i) > \epsilon$ for any $\epsilon > 0$ and therefore more difficult to accurately estimate $P(\mathbf{x}_i)$ using an unbiased sampling distribution.

3.5.4 Estimating the Conditional Entropy

For both, marginal entropy and conditional entropy we have to evaluate the likelihood $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ a total of $N_s N_x$ times. To compare the accuracy of we performed estimates of the marginal entropy with and without optimized sampling together with estimates of the conditional entropy for $N_s = 1000$ and $N_x = 25600$. In fig. 3.10 we show the relative error of both, marginal and conditional entropy estimates as a function of the sparsity. We find that the estimate of the conditional entropy is very accurate regardless of sampling size. Even with optimized sampling the marginal entropy estimate is roughly two orders of magnitude worse than a comparable conditional entropy estimate.

3.6 Discussion

Since both the estimate of the marginal entropy and of the conditional entropy require the computation of two nested Monte Carlo averages one could expect the results of both estimates to be of similar accuracy. Yet we find that computing the marginal entropy is much more challenging than computing the conditional entropy. While analyzing the estimation procedure for the marginal entropy we found the main source of error to arise from the computation of the marginal probability density $P(\mathbf{x})$. The computation of this density suffers from high Monte Carlo variance when we are not carefully optimizing our trajectory sampling procedure. We fail to sample those signals that actually contribute to the marginal probability density. This leads to a biased estimate of $P(\mathbf{x})$ since we under-estimate the integral $\int ds P(\mathbf{s}) P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$. We see the existence of this bias in our results since we consistently over-estimate the marginal entropy.

We can thus conclude that the main difficulty of obtaining a good estimate for the mutual information between trajectories lies in the efficient and accurate computation of the marginal entropy. A viable approach for this seems to be to use importance sampling in the signal space in the computation of the marginal probability density. Our results indicate that such an approach could also work for trajectories generated using a fully stochastic model of a biochemical network.

4 Directed Sampling in Trajectory Space

In the previous chapters we established a technique to compute the mutual information between time-variable signals and responses using Monte-Carlo integration together with stochastic simulations. In practice we found that this method often severely over-estimates the mutual information. In the previous chapter we came to the conclusion that the root of the biased estimates is the computation of the marginal probability density $P(\mathbf{x})$.

The fundamental identity for the prediction of model parameters \mathbf{s} given some data or response \mathbf{x} is Bayes' theorem

$$P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) P(\mathbf{s})}{P(\mathbf{x})} \quad (4.1)$$

which describes how the observation of \mathbf{x} changes the probability distribution for the signals from $P(\mathbf{s})$ to $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})$. In statistics, one usually denotes $P(\mathbf{s})$ as the *prior*, $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ as the *likelihood*, $P(\mathbf{x})$ as the *evidence* (or *marginal likelihood*) and $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})$ as the *posterior* distribution. It is no accident that for the description of statistical inference we reuse the same letters \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{s} as in the previous chapters. Indeed, at its core, the biochemical network performs statistical inference of the signal from the data given by its response. Thus, for now, we are going to change the perspective and look at the problem through the eyes of a Bayesian statistician.

From the statistician's point of view, we have a *model* with a set of parameters $\mathbf{s} = (s_1, s_2, \dots)^T$ that we want to fit to the observations or data \mathbf{x} . The Bayesian approach involves choosing a reasonable *prior*, i.e. making an educated guess for the distribution $P(\mathbf{s})$ using justifiable assumptions about the underlying system. Using eq. (4.1), the statistician can compute the *posterior* probability distribution of the model parameters $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})$ from the observations \mathbf{x} . This involves computing the *likelihood* $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ and the *evidence* $P(\mathbf{x})$ of the acquired data \mathbf{x} for the given model. Usually, models are chosen that make it easy to compute the likelihood of some data given the model parameters. It is the computation of the *evidence* $P(\mathbf{x})$ which usually requires more sophisticated computational methods [28]. In most cases, the evidence is estimated using the identity $P(\mathbf{x}) =$

$\int ds P(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})$ which has motivated the use of the term *marginal likelihood*. In the following section we show the evolution of methods to compute such integrals in statistical science.

4.1 Previous Work on the Computation of the Marginal Likelihood

The estimation of the marginal density $P(\mathbf{x}) = \int ds P(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})$ is an important ingredient for Bayesian statistics, and is used for example in the computation of so-called *Bayes factors* for hypothesis testing.

Written as

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = \langle P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) \rangle_{P(\mathbf{s})} \quad (4.2)$$

the marginal density is an example of an expectation value with respect to a potentially complex distribution. For simple distributions, expectations can be approximated by a simple Monte-Carlo approach, taking the sample average $1/N \sum_{i=1}^N P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}_i)$ of N independent random samples $\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_N$ generated from $P(\mathbf{s})$. That is, we estimate the marginal density using samples from the *prior* and averaging over their likelihoods. As demonstrated in the previous chapters, this method is not very efficient when the individual signals \mathbf{s}_i are actually trajectories. Once the space of possible signals is sufficiently large it becomes extremely unlikely to sample a \mathbf{s}' such that $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}')$ presents a strong contribution to the mean. A well-known approach to circumvent this problem is *importance sampling*.

4.1.1 Importance Sampling

In importance sampling, we choose a different distribution than the prior from which to generate samples. Let $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_1, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{s}}_N$ be samples drawn from a distribution with a known density function \hat{q} . Then we can estimate eq. (4.2) as

$$\hat{P}^{(q)}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{P(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i) P(\mathbf{x}|\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i)}{\hat{q}(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i)} \equiv \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{q(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i)}{\hat{q}(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_i)} \quad (4.3)$$

where by $q(\mathbf{s}) = P(\mathbf{s}) P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ we denote the unnormalized posterior distribution (note that the posterior is $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}) = q(\mathbf{s})/C$ with $C = P(\mathbf{x})$). This is precisely the approach that was described

in sec. 3.5.3 using the term *umbrella sampling*. For this section we will continue to use the statisticians' terminology of *importance sampling*. The choice of \hat{q} requires crucial consideration for eq. (4.3) to yield a good estimate. To reduce the variance of the ratio $q(\hat{s}_i)/\hat{q}(\hat{s}_i)$, the sampling distribution \hat{q} should be similar to the posterior and have tails no thinner than q [29]. In practice it is often very difficult to find an adequate choice for \hat{q} , especially in high-dimensional spaces. Therefore, it has been suggested to choose an appropriate sampling function using one or more *posterior samples* i.e. random samples taken from the posterior distribution $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})$ [25,29–31]. Even if it is possible to acquire a sufficient amount of posterior samples, these methods usually require the choice of an appropriate parametric family of distributions from which the sampling distribution is picked. Since in our case, the individual \mathbf{s} are entire trajectories it is unclear what a useful family of distributions in trajectory space would be.

Some authors have instead proposed methods to compute the marginal density *directly* from the posterior samples without the need to pick a separate sampling distribution \hat{q} . This promises to be more efficient than using prior samples since we don't face the problem of generating mostly irrelevant signals for a given response. However, the generation of random samples from $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})$ is often a non-trivial problem. Thus, there have been proposed a variety of Markov chain Monte Carlo methods to generate approximately independent samples from the posterior distribution [27,32–35]. We will leave the discussion of efficient posterior sampling for later and assume for now to have a set of corresponding samples available.

4.1.2 Estimating the Marginal Density from Posterior Samples

Let $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_N$ be independent posterior draws. Newton, et. al. [36] propose the harmonic mean estimator

$$\hat{p}^{(\text{harm.})}(\mathbf{x}) = \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N P(\mathbf{x}|\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i)^{-1} \right]^{-1}, \quad (4.4)$$

i.e. the marginal likelihood is estimated by the harmonic mean of the likelihoods of a sample from the posterior distribution. It has been noted that this estimate is rather unstable because of the occasional occurrence of a value $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i$ with a small likelihood and hence a large effect on the final result [36]. The estimate in eq. (4.4) can therefore be improved using an arbitrary probability

density f as proposed by Gelfand, et. al. [37]

$$\hat{p}^{(\text{reciprocal})}(\mathbf{x}) = \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{f(\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i)}{q(\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i)} \right]^{-1}. \quad (4.5)$$

If we choose $f(\mathbf{s}) = P(\mathbf{s})$ we recover the harmonic rule in eq. (4.4). If instead, we choose f with tails thinner than q this estimator is well-behaved [29]. This requirement for f is the opposite as for importance sampling which lead to the estimate in eq. (4.5) being called *reciprocal importance sampling*. However, similarly as before it is often difficult to find a density f that has sufficiently thin tails in all dimensions. Both, importance sampling and reciprocal importance sampling are special cases of a more general identity.

4.1.3 Bridge Sampling and Beyond

The idea of bridge sampling was first given by Bennet [38] for the simulation of free energy differences. Given two unnormalized probability densities, q_1 and q_2 , Meng and Wong [39] state the central identity of bridge sampling as

$$\frac{c_1}{c_2} = \frac{\langle q_1(\mathbf{s}) \alpha(\mathbf{s}) \rangle_2}{\langle q_2(\mathbf{s}) \alpha(\mathbf{s}) \rangle_1} \quad (4.6)$$

where c_1, c_2 are the normalization constants corresponding to q_1, q_2 , and α is an arbitrary function. $\langle \cdot \rangle_i$ denotes the expectation with respect to the distribution corresponding to q_i . If we choose $q_1(\mathbf{s}) = q(\mathbf{s})$ and $q_2(\mathbf{s}) = \hat{q}(\mathbf{s})$ then for $\alpha(\mathbf{s}) = 1/\hat{q}(\mathbf{s})$ we get importance sampling as defined in eq. (4.3). If we choose $\alpha(\mathbf{s}) = [q_1(\mathbf{s}) q_2(\mathbf{s})]^{-1}$ we get

$$\frac{c_1}{c_2} = \frac{\langle q_2^{-1}(\mathbf{s}) \rangle_2}{\langle q_1^{-1}(\mathbf{s}) \rangle_1} \quad (4.7)$$

which is a generalization of the harmonic rule in eq. (4.4).

For bridge sampling, Bennet, Meng and Wong [38,39] discuss optimal choices for α such that the mean square error of the estimate is minimized. It turns out that a good choice of α acts as a *bridge* between the densities q_1 and q_2 , such that both the numerator and the denominator of eq. (4.6) can be reliably computed. Hence, the name: bridge sampling.

It did not go unnoticed that techniques originally developed for the computation of free energy differences might be useful in Bayesian computation. Gelman and Weng [40] introduce *path*

sampling which is a generalized form of *thermodynamic integration*. It takes the idea of bridge sampling one step further: instead of using one bridge to join two distributions q_1 and q_2 and compute the ratio of their normalization constants, thermodynamic integration constructs a continuous *path in distribution space* between q_1 and q_2 to further increase the efficiency. Another related method is *annealed importance sampling*, proposed by Neal [34]. It is based on simulated annealing, another technique originating in statistical physics.

We have seen that many methods to compute the marginal likelihood draw inspiration from statistical physics. Specifically we can map the computation of the normalization constant of a probability distribution to the simulation of free energy differences. In the next subsection we will introduce notation and terminology reminiscent of Statistical physics to describe our problem. In this way we can understand why those methods are so helpful for Bayesian computation. Using that description we show that both, Thermodynamic Integration and the Wang-Landau algorithm are very promising candidates for the computation of $P(\mathbf{x})$.

4.2 Borrowing Terminology from Statistical Physics

The mutual information then measures the difference in entropies between these two distributions or in other words: *how much uncertainty about \mathbf{s} the observation of \mathbf{x} was able to remove*. For the computation of the *mutual information* between \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} we need to estimate the marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X})$ which requires averaging over the logarithm of the marginal densities $\ln P(\mathbf{x}_i)$ for many samples $\mathbf{x}_i \sim \mathcal{X}$. Since we only have access to the *prior* and the *likelihood* we have to compute the marginal likelihood as $P(\mathbf{x}) = \int ds P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})P(\mathbf{s})$. These kinds of integrals are very familiar to researchers in statistical physics albeit them using a different terminology to describe them. In the following we will describe how eq. (4.1) is analogous to the distribution of the canonical ensemble and how this analogy allows us to make use of efficient computational methods from statistical physics.

In the framework employed by statistical physics, Bayes' theorem corresponds to the canonical ensemble distribution of \mathbf{s} (for $\beta = 1$)

$$P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{Z(\mathbf{x})} \exp[-E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})] \quad (4.8)$$

where the *partition function* is defined by $Z(\mathbf{x}) = \int ds \exp[-E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})]$ and $E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})$ denotes the total energy of the system at state \mathbf{s} . In this context \mathbf{x} is considered a parameter vector for the specific

model used to compute the energy. In classical problems of statistical physics (such as e.g. the *Ising model*) the state space spans the single particle states $\mathbf{s} = (\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n) \in \Omega^n$ for all particles and the energy is given by the *Hamiltonian* $\mathcal{H}(\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n; \mathbf{x})$ where \mathbf{x} could contain parameters describing e.g. the interaction strength between neighboring spins. In our case however we define our energy function by comparison with eq. (4.1) as

$$E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x}) = -\ln P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) - \ln P(\mathbf{s}). \quad (4.9)$$

From this point of view the marginal density $P(\mathbf{x}) = Z(\mathbf{x})$ is the partition function of the canonical ensemble. In statistical physics the partition function is of central importance since its partial derivatives include all thermodynamic properties of a physical system. The free energy of the canonical ensemble is defined by $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}) = -\ln Z(\mathbf{x})$ (for $\beta = 1$) such that using this terminology we can write the marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X})$ as an average over the “*free energies of response trajectories*”

$$H(\mathcal{X}) = \int d\mathbf{x} P(\mathbf{x}) \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \langle \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}) \rangle_{P(\mathbf{x})}. \quad (4.10)$$

Since the computation of the partition function is central to the solution of many statistical problems there has been done considerable work on efficient estimation of the partition function, the free energy and other related quantities such as the *density of states*.

4.3 Thermodynamic Integration

One well-established technique to estimate free energy (differences) is by thermodynamic integration (TI) [40]. It allows the accurate computation of the ratio between the normalization constants of two different probability distributions using a continuous path in *distribution space* that connects both. Since this strategy uses random samples taken from many different distributions along this path it is especially robust when the two distributions have very little overlap. For the computation of the marginal density $P(\mathbf{x})$ we can (for a given \mathbf{x}) define a suitable path in distribution space between $P(\mathbf{s})$ and $P(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})$. The normalization constants of these distributions are $z_0 = 1$ and $z_1 = P(\mathbf{x})$, respectively such that the ratio $r = z_1/z_0$ of these normalization constants directly corresponds to the marginal density. Using TI we estimate this ratio using approximately independent samples from a *Markov chain Monte Carlo* (MCMC) simulation.

In the following sections we will give a quick summary of TI followed by an explanation of the Markov chain Monte Carlo simulation and a discussion of the resulting accuracy of the estimates.

4.3.1 Summary of the Technique

Let q_0 and q_1 be the unnormalized distribution functions and z_0, z_1 the corresponding normalization constants such that $z_i = \int ds q_i(\mathbf{s})$. Next we construct a path between q_0 and q_1 , parametrized by $\theta \in [0, 1]$ such that q_θ smoothly connects the end points. We similarly define $z(\theta)$ as the normalization constant of q_θ . A smooth path that can be constructed for any pair of distributions (q_0, q_1) is the *geometric path* given by $q_\theta = q_0^{1-\theta} q_1^\theta$. Note however that variance of the estimate depends on the chosen path and that the geometric path is not the optimal path in general.

For the estimation of free energy differences we are interested in the ratio $r = z(1)/z(0)$. To find an estimate we differentiate the logarithm of $z(\theta)$ with respect to θ to arrive at

$$\frac{d \ln z(\theta)}{d\theta} = \frac{1}{z(\theta)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \int ds q_\theta(\mathbf{s}) = \int ds \frac{q_\theta(\mathbf{s})}{z(\theta)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \ln q_\theta(\mathbf{s}) = \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \ln q_\theta(\mathbf{s}) \right\rangle_{p_\theta(\mathbf{s})} \quad (4.11)$$

where $p_\theta(\mathbf{s}) = q_\theta(\mathbf{s})/z(\theta)$ is the normalized probability distribution corresponding to q_θ . By analogy to the potential in statistical physics we define

$$U(\mathbf{s}, \theta) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \ln q_\theta(\mathbf{s}). \quad (4.12)$$

Now we can express the log-ratio $\lambda = \ln r$ by the integral

$$\lambda = \ln z(1) - \ln z(0) = -\int_0^1 d\theta \langle U(\mathbf{s}, \theta) \rangle_{p_\theta(\mathbf{s})} \quad (4.13)$$

which forms the basis of all thermodynamic integration estimates. One advantage of the TI estimators is that we directly estimate the log-ratio λ , i.e. the free energy difference as opposed to the ratio of partition functions. Indeed, to eventually compute the marginal entropy $H(\mathcal{X}) = -\langle \ln P(\mathbf{x}) \rangle$ we require the logarithm of the marginal density thus no further error is introduced by taking the logarithm of an estimated quantity.

Using the previous identities, one possible way to estimate λ is to regard θ as a random variable with a density $p(\theta)$, allowing us to compute the integral in eq. (4.13) using the Monte Carlo estimator

$$\hat{\lambda}_{\text{MC}} = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{U(\mathbf{s}_i, \theta_i)}{p(\theta_i)} \quad (4.14)$$

with draws $(\mathbf{s}_1, \theta_1), \dots, (\mathbf{s}_n, \theta_n)$ from the joint probability density $p(\mathbf{s}, \theta) = p_\theta(\mathbf{s}) p(\theta)$. Alternatively, we can perform numerical integration using the trapezoidal rule by evaluating the potential over values $\theta_1 < \dots < \theta_{n-1}$ between $\theta_0 = 0$ and $\theta_n = 1$

$$\hat{\lambda}_{\text{NI}} = -\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\langle U(\mathbf{s}, \theta_{i-1}) \rangle_{p_{\theta_{i-1}}(\mathbf{s})} + \langle U(\mathbf{s}, \theta_i) \rangle_{p_{\theta_i}(\mathbf{s})}}{2} (\theta_i - \theta_{i-1}) \quad (4.15)$$

where each average over the potential is performed using a Monte Carlo simulation.

To use these estimators for the computation of the marginal density $P(\mathbf{x})$ at a given \mathbf{x} we need to construct a path between the densities $q_0(\mathbf{s}) = P(\mathbf{s})$ and $q_1(\mathbf{s}) = P(\mathbf{s})P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$. For simplicity and convenience we choose the geometric path $q_\theta(\mathbf{s}) = P(\mathbf{s}) [P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})]^\theta$. Taking the logarithm of this density we get $\ln q_\theta(\mathbf{s}) = \ln P(\mathbf{s}) + \theta \ln P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ which prompts us to define the “energy” of a signal trajectory with respect to θ as

$$E(\mathbf{s}, \theta) = -\ln q_\theta(\mathbf{s}) = -\ln P(\mathbf{s}) - \theta \ln P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}). \quad (4.16)$$

For $\theta = 1$ this definition of the energy matches our previous definition by analogy with the canonical ensemble whereas for $\theta = 0$ this definition of the energy is equivalent to the energy of a signal trajectory for a system where \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} are completely independent and thus $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x}) = P(\mathbf{s})$. Thus, this nomenclature also motivates the name “potential” for the quantity

$$U(\mathbf{s}, \theta) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \ln q_\theta(\mathbf{s}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} E_\theta(\mathbf{s}) = -\ln P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}) \quad (4.17)$$

i.e. θ acts as a “knob” that allows us to gradually turn the potential on or off. The potential term itself characterizes the amount of dependence between the random variables \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{X} . Note that all energetic quantities depend on the specific response \mathbf{x} (except at $\theta = 0$) even if this dependence is suppressed in the notation.

To use the TI estimators introduced in eqns. (4.14) and (4.15) we need to generate samples from arbitrary distributions along our chosen geometric path. Since we can compute the unnormalized densities of these distributions, we can use the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm as a very general method to sample from arbitrary distributions [41].

Figure 4.1: Visualization of the log-likelihoods $\ln P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ and the acceptance rates $\frac{\text{accepted}}{\text{accepted}+\text{rejected}}$ during individual Monte-Carlo runs. Each MCMC run used a different value for θ , randomly chosen from the uniform distribution between 0 and 1. The x -axis shows the sample numbers 1 to 100. Between one sample and the next one we skip 1000 accept-reject steps for which no statistics were collected.

4.3.2 Markov Chain Monte Carlo

To generate approximately independent samples from a distribution given by the unnormalized density q_θ we start from an (in principle arbitrary) initial signal \mathbf{s} . Next, a new signal \mathbf{s}' is proposed from the proposal distribution $T(\mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}')$ which is typically chosen to yield a \mathbf{s}' close to \mathbf{s} . Then with some probability $A(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{s})$ we *accept* the new configuration and our first generated sample is $\mathbf{s}_1 = \mathbf{s}'$. Otherwise we *reject* the new configuration and our first sample is equal to the initial signal $\mathbf{s}_1 = \mathbf{s}$. For the next iteration of the algorithm we then set our new initial signal to be $\mathbf{s} \leftarrow \mathbf{s}_1$ such that when we repeat this procedure many times we generate a sequence of signals $\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \dots$ where each sample is a random value only directly dependent on the immediately preceding sample. Thus we have defined a Markov process that generates a *chain* of signals with the transition probability given by $P(\mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}') = T(\mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}')A(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{s})$. We want to choose the acceptance probability $A(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{s})$ such that the stationary distribution of this Markov process is precisely q_θ . It can be shown that the *Metropolis choice*

$$A(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}') = \min\left(1, \frac{q_\theta(\mathbf{s}') T(\mathbf{s}' \rightarrow \mathbf{s})}{q_\theta(\mathbf{s}) T(\mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}')}\right) \quad (4.18)$$

leads to the correct stationary distribution given that the system is ergodic.

For the Gaussian system we choose the proposal distribution $T(\mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}')$ to be a multivariate

Figure 4.2: Comparison of the covariance matrices obtained a) by computing the empirical covariance of 1000 approximately uncorrelated samples taken from the MCMC procedure (for $\theta = 1$) and b) by analytically computing the covariance matrix of the normal distribution $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})$. The proposal distribution is a multivariate normal distribution with covariance $\Sigma = \sigma^{-2}\mathbb{I}$, with a value of $\sigma = 0.01$.

Figure 4.3: Samples of the averaged potential for different values of θ . There are 216 samples for values of θ chosen uniformly distributed in the interval $[0, 1]$. Every point is an individual MCMC simulation with 1000 approximately independent draws. The bars on the right show a histogram of the log-likelihoods. The TI estimate is the integral from $\theta = 0$ to 1 of the curve that the individual samples approximate. Using the estimate from eq. (4.14), the estimated value differs by merely 0.012 % from the analytically correct value of $P(\mathbf{x})$. This shows that given enough samples, TI is able to provide very accurate results for the marginal density.

normal distribution centered around \mathbf{s} and with uniform covariance $\Sigma = \sigma^{-2}\mathbb{I}$. In fig. 4.2 we show that using the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm we can generate samples with an appropriate distribution that matches the analytical expectation. In fig. 4.3 we show the averaged potentials for 216 MCMC runs for different values of θ . From these potentials we can compute the marginal density using the estimator from eq. (4.14). The results are very promising since the estimated value differs by merely 0.012 % from the analytically correct value of $P(\mathbf{x})$.

4.4 Estimating the Density of States

In the context of statistical physics we often look at configurations of a system that can be described by a configuration $\mathbf{n} \in \Omega$ where Ω is the state space of the system. We can typically assign a probability (density) to each configuration. For example, let's consider the canonical ensemble for a given inverse temperature β and Hamiltonian \mathcal{H}

$$P(\mathbf{n}) = \frac{1}{Z(\beta)} e^{-\beta \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n})} \quad (4.19)$$

with the *partition function* $Z(\beta) = \int d\mathbf{n} e^{-\beta \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n})}$. The Hamiltonian assigns an energy to every state, i.e. for every state \mathbf{n} we have an associated energy $\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n})$. To learn more about the distribution of energies in our system we can now define the *density of states* $g(E)$ which is proportional to the number of states with energy E . More precisely, let \mathcal{N} be a random variable uniformly distributed in the state space, then

$$g(E) = P(\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{N}) = E) . \quad (4.20)$$

While the density of states (*DOS*) thus describes the number of states at individual energy levels, the Boltzmann factor $e^{-\beta E}$ specifies the relative weight of states with energy E in the canonical ensemble. That is, we can compute the ensemble average $\langle f(\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n})) \rangle$ of any function f that depends only on the energy of a given state as

$$\langle f(\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n})) \rangle = \frac{\int_{\Omega} d\mathbf{n} f(\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n})) e^{-\beta \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n})}}{\int_{\Omega} d\mathbf{n} e^{-\beta \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n})}} = \frac{\int dE f(E) g(E) e^{-\beta E}}{\int dE g(E) e^{-\beta E}} \quad (4.21)$$

where $\int_{\Omega} d\mathbf{n}$ denotes an integral over phase space. Eq. (4.21) motivates the common way of specifying the DOS using the Dirac delta function

$$g(E) = \int_{\Omega} d\mathbf{n} \delta(\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n}) - E) \quad (4.22)$$

which matches the intuition of plotting an energy histogram for uniformly chosen states. I.e. for discrete energies $E_1 < \dots < E_n$ (the histogram bins) and random states $\mathbf{n}_1, \dots, \mathbf{n}_N$ we can approximate the DOS as

$$g_{\text{discrete}}(E_i) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \delta_{\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n}_j), E_i} \quad (4.23)$$

where δ_{ϵ, E_i} is 1 if the energy ϵ falls inside the i -th histogram bin and 0 otherwise. As the number of random states and the number of histogram bins grow towards infinity, g_{discrete} converges to eq. (4.22).

For us, the DOS is of relevance because can be used to compute the partition function

$$Z(\beta) = \int_{\Omega} d\mathbf{n} e^{-\beta H(\mathbf{n})} = \int dE g(E) e^{-\beta E} \quad (4.24)$$

and thus the free energy. In the following we will discuss the Wang and Landau algorithm to estimate the DOS and evaluate its usefulness for the computation of the marginal density of a trajectory.

4.4.1 Wang and Landau Algorithm

Since the state spaces Ω are usually very large, one typically resorts to Monte-Carlo methods to estimate the density of states. There one generates a sequence of states \mathbf{n}_i that are approximately independent and distributed according to $P(\mathcal{N})$, e.g. by using the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm. For every sampled state \mathbf{n}_i we can compute the Energy $\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n}_i)$ and then approximate the density of states by a histogram of the energy values as in eq. (4.23). To get an accurate estimate of the density of states for energy values E where $g(E)$ is very small we need a lot of iterations since we will on average pick very few samples with low probability.

The approach of Wang and Landau [42,43] is instead to not generate samples that are distributed according to the equilibrium distribution $P(\mathbf{n})$ but to adaptively vary the sampling distribution throughout the simulation. This is done such that for every energy value E approximately the same number of samples are acquired such that the DOS can be accurately estimated even in regions of low density $g(E)$.

The main idea is to perform a random walk in energy space such that on average all energy levels in a predefined interval are visited equally often. If we switch from energy space to state space this implies that the probability density for this random walk to visit a state \mathbf{n} is proportional to the reciprocal density of states $1/g[\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{n})]$. Of course we can't sample directly using the reciprocal DOS since it is unknown. Instead, at each step of the algorithm we slightly alter our sampling distribution until the histogram of energy values becomes *flat*. Once the histogram is

flat we conclude that the adaptively altered sampling distribution represents precisely the reciprocal DOS.

To perform Wang-Landau sampling we have to define energy bins E_1, \dots, E_n that represent the range of energies that we want to compute the DOS for. We start by setting $g(E_i) = 1$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$. Then—similarly to Metropolis-Hastings sampling—we iteratively propose and selectively accept new configurations such that the transition probability from energy level $E_i \rightarrow E_j$ is

$$p(E_i \rightarrow E_j) = \min\left(1, \frac{g(E_i)}{g(E_j)}\right). \quad (4.25)$$

After each proposal we update a histogram of visited energies $H(E_j) \leftarrow H(E_j) + 1$ and modify the density of states at E_j by a constant factor $g(E_j) \leftarrow f g(E_j)$. This updating of the sampling distribution during the simulation is precisely what makes the random walk non-Markovian and promises fast convergence towards the correct DOS. We start the procedure with the factor $f = \exp(1) = e$. Once the histogram $H(E)$ is sufficiently flat (we use 95% flatness) we update $f \leftarrow \sqrt{f}$ and reset the histogram to continue sampling. We continue the simulation, iteratively reducing f until it reaches a small predefined threshold value which allows us to adjust the tradeoff between accuracy and simulation speed.

One important consideration is the choice of energy bins. Since we are interested in the computation of the partition function using eq. (4.24), the relevant energies are those where the product $g(E)e^{-\beta E}$ is not vanishingly small. Additionally we have to take into account that the estimate for the DOS is not normalized. To be able to correctly normalize the DOS we have to ensure that the range of energy bins includes all energies where the DOS is non-vanishing.

4.4.2 Applying Wang-Landau to the Computation of the Marginal Density

Modified DOS

When working with statistical models such as the Ising model there is often a clear concept of the *state space* Ω and an associated volume of regions in state space such that integrals of the form $\int_{\Omega} d\mathbf{n} f(\mathbf{n})$ are well-defined for any $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. However in the case where the individual states \mathbf{n} represent stochastic trajectories it is not obvious what the meaning of such an integral

should be. Therefore we use a modified DOS defined for a given response trajectory \mathbf{x} by

$$\rho(U) = \int ds P(\mathbf{s}) \delta(U(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x}) - U) \quad (4.26)$$

with $U(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x}) = -\ln P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$. In other words we are assigning a measure μ to our state space which is defined by the inherent probability density of the signals, such that $\int \mu(ds) \equiv \int ds P(\mathbf{s})$. Thus we can express the marginal density of \mathbf{x} analogously to eq. (4.24) by

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = \int dU \rho(U) e^{-U}. \quad (4.27)$$

Modified Wang-Landau algorithm

We have to slightly adapt the Wang-Landau procedure described above so that it produces an estimate of the modified DOS. To account for the density $P(\mathbf{s})$ in eq. (4.26) we need ensure we propose configurations, asymptotically distributed according to $P(\mathbf{s})$, which we then—in a second step—accept or reject using the inverse DOS. However we can combine both of these steps into a single one by combining a Metropolis acceptance step with the usual Wang-Landau procedure. Our algorithm therefore consists of the following steps:

1. Set all entries of the modified DOS to 1, $\rho(U_i) = 1, i = 1, \dots, n$.
2. Set all entries of the histogram to 0, $H(U_i) = 0, i = 1, \dots, n$.
3. Loop until $f < \epsilon$.

1. Propose a new configuration $\mathbf{s}' \sim T(\mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}')$.
2. Let U_i be the potential of state \mathbf{s} and U_j the potential of state \mathbf{s}' .
3. Accept the new configuration with probability

$$A(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{s}) = \min \left[1, \frac{P(\mathbf{s}') \rho(U_i) T(\mathbf{s}' \rightarrow \mathbf{s})}{P(\mathbf{s}) \rho(U_j) T(\mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}')} \right]. \quad (4.28)$$

4. Let U^* be either U_j if \mathbf{s}' was accepted or U_i otherwise.
5. Update the histogram $H(U^*) \leftarrow H(U^*) + 1$ and the DOS $\rho(U^*) \leftarrow f \rho(U^*)$.
6. If the histogram H is flat, set $f \leftarrow \sqrt{f}$ and reset $H(U_i) = 0, i = 1, \dots, n$.

The proposal distribution T can in principle be arbitrary. The definition of the acceptance probability in eq. (4.28) illustrates that—once the simulation is converged— ρ describes how we have to modify the state space density $P(\mathbf{s})$ such that we sample uniformly over all potentials.

Comparison to usual Wang-Landau algorithm

Usually the Wang-Landau algorithm is used to estimate the regular DOS $g(E) = \int ds \delta(E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x}) - E)$ where $E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x}) = -\ln P(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})$. We can easily verify that algebraically this definition of $E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})$ satisfies equation eq. (4.24) such that

$$Z = P(\mathbf{x}) = \int dE g(E) e^{-E}. \quad (4.29)$$

The Wang-Landau algorithm to compute the DOS $g(E)$ would be the same as the ones described above with the sole difference being the acceptance rate which would instead be

$$\tilde{A}(\mathbf{s}', \mathbf{s}) = \min \left[1, \frac{\rho(U_i) T(\mathbf{s}' \rightarrow \mathbf{s})}{\rho(U_j) T(\mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}')} \right]. \quad (4.30)$$

The difference between eq. (4.28) and eq. (4.30) precisely reflects the fact that $\rho(E)$ and $g(E)$ are defined using different integration measures ($\rho(E)$ includes $P(\mathbf{s})$ in its integral in eq. (4.26) while $g(E)$ does not). However the regular version of the Wang-Landau algorithm can't be used in practice to compute the marginal density in the multivariate normal system that we are using since the regular DOS grows without bound as $E \rightarrow \infty$: In our case the joint distribution $P(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x})$ is a multivariate normal distribution in $2d$ dimensions such that for any number $\epsilon > 0$ there exists a $2d$ -dimensional ellipsoid that contains all points such that $E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x}) \leq \epsilon$. The DOS $g(\epsilon)$ is precisely the volume of the $2d - 1$ dimensional surface of this ellipsoid. As we increase ϵ the size of the ellipsoid also keeps increasing such that $\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow \infty} g(\epsilon) = \infty$. This behavior of the regular DOS makes it impossible to use the Wang-Landau algorithm to compute $g(E)$ since by its design the algorithm merely estimates the unnormalized DOS. For this reason we have to modify the DOS as is done in eq. (4.26) which ensures that we can normalize the result of the Wang-Landau algorithm.

Connection to Standard Monte-Carlo Sampling

When we perform a standard Monte-Carlo estimate of $P(\mathbf{x})$ we generate independent samples $\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_M$, all identically distributed according to $P(\mathbf{s})$ and then compute

$$\hat{P}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s}_i). \quad (4.31)$$

Figure 4.4: Illustrating the benefit of using the Wang-Landau algorithm for the multivariate normal system at different dimensionalities: The blue lines show the modified density of states from eq. (4.26), computed using a conventional MC simulation. The orange line represents the Boltzmann factor e^{-U} and the green line shows the integrand of eq. (4.27) which is the product of the other two quantities. For visualization purposes, all functions were rescaled such that their integrals over the displayed interval equal 1. We see that especially at higher dimensionality there is very little overlap between the green and the blue line which leads to high inaccuracy in the computation of the marginal density. For all simulations we chose the covariance matrix using $\Delta t = 64$.

This estimate is essentially the same as performing the integral from eq. (4.27) where the density of states $\rho(U)$ is just approximated as the histogram of the potentials $U(\mathbf{s}_1), \dots, U(\mathbf{s}_M)$. Specifically in the limit of the width of histogram bins approaching 0, the approximate modified density of states becomes $\hat{\rho}(U) = 1/M \sum_{i=1}^M \delta(U - U(\mathbf{s}_i))$ and therefore

$$\int dU \hat{\rho}(U) e^{-U} = \frac{1}{M} \int dU \left[\sum_{i=1}^M \delta(U - U(\mathbf{s}_i)) e^{-U} \right] = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M e^{-U(\mathbf{s}_i)} = \hat{P}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (4.32)$$

For the purpose of comparing estimates we can therefore associate the standard MC approach with computing the empirical histogram of potential values when sampling signals according to their marginal distribution. In the next section we will compare this empirical histogram to the DOS as computed using the Wang-Landau algorithm.

Figure 4.5: Plots of estimates of the modified DOS from eq. (4.26) compared on both linear and log scales. The blue line shows the Wang-Landau estimate while the orange line is a histogram estimate using unbiased sampling according to $P(\mathbf{s})$. We see that especially in the low-potential regime the Wang-Landau estimate is much more accurate.

4.4.3 Example Results for a Wang-Landau Simulation

Fig. 4.4 makes it clear why we expect Wang-Landau sampling to lead to a better estimate of the marginal density than the brute-force Monte-Carlo computation, especially in high-dimensional state spaces. For $d = 50$ and $d = 200$ most of the weight of the integral is in regions where $\rho(E) \approx 0$. In these low density regions we usually get a very inaccurate estimation of the (modified) DOS by normal MC simulations since we only very occasionally sample a relevant state. The Wang-Landau algorithm ensures that for every energy there is a consistent sampling density and we get a good estimate of the DOS even in low-density regimes.

From fig. 4.4 we can also estimate for which range of potentials we must compute the DOS. Since the Boltzmann weight e^{-U} strongly favors low-potential configurations it is important to compute the DOS for very low potentials even if it nearly vanishes there (i.e. in regions where the blue line vanishes but the green line has relevant weight).

In fig. 4.5 we display the estimated DOS using the Wang-Landau algorithm compared with a histogram estimate of the DOS using unbiased sampling. We see that in the highly relevant

regime of low potential the Wang-Landau procedure allows us to get an accurate estimate of the DOS even though its density is as low as $e^{-45} \approx 10^{-20}$. Using eq. (4.27) we compute the marginal density to be -664.01 whereas the “correct” value computed analytically is -664.24 . We thus find a relative error of 0.03% in this estimate.

We have found two methods, thermodynamic integration and Wang-Landau sampling to show very promising results for the estimation of the marginal density. So far however, we have only tested these methods using the Gaussian approximation where it is especially easy to generate trial moves to be used in the MCMC schemes. Since in the Gaussian approximation a trajectory is described by a d -dimensional vector $\mathbf{s} = (s^1, \dots, s^d)^T \in \mathbb{R}^d$ we can simply generate a small displacement vector $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^d$ from an appropriate multivariate normal with sufficiently small covariance such that we have a proposal $\mathbf{s}' = (s^1 + \xi^1, \dots, s^d + \xi^d)$. Given a symmetric distribution of displacements, the proposal is naturally also symmetric. With all that said, using the Gaussian approximation we can only describe a fairly limited range of stochastic processes. Since the signal dynamics are fully characterized by their first- and second-order statistics it fails to describe non-Markovian or discrete signals. Going beyond the Gaussian approximation, we are interested in signals that are described by a general stochastic differential equation (SDE). In the next section we will therefore explore some ideas for the generation of appropriate trial moves for such general stochastic trajectories.

4.5 Generating Proposal Trajectories from General Stochastic Dynamics

Hence, our goal is, given a trajectory \mathbf{s}_n , to generate a correlated trajectory \mathbf{s}_{n+1} such that a long sequence of chained proposals $\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \dots$ would converge towards a specific distribution. For both, thermodynamic integration and Wang-Landau sampling we can write that distribution as $e^{-E(\mathbf{s})}$ where $E(\mathbf{s}) = -\ln P(\mathbf{s}) + U(\mathbf{s})$. The term $U(\mathbf{s})$ varies between the methods, and in both cases it skews the sampling distribution towards the posterior distribution $P(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{x})$. If the signal dynamics are described by a stochastic differential equation (SDE) we can numerically generate independent samples from the prior distribution $P(\mathbf{s})$ but there is no straightforward way to generate independent samples from a slightly altered distribution. In this section we are therefore going to show how we can generate a proposal trajectory \mathbf{s}_{n+1} by partly modifying \mathbf{s}_n together

with an acceptance/rejection step to ensure the correct distribution. Since we generate a new trajectory by modifying an existing one, \mathbf{s}_{n+1} is naturally correlated with \mathbf{s}_n .

The idea is to modify the initial trajectory \mathbf{s}_n by *regrowing* parts of it. The terminology of *regrowing* is frequently used to describe trial moves where we replace a segment of the trajectory with a new one that we generate on the fly. In other words, we cut out an existing segment of \mathbf{s}_n , and regrow the hole by using the SDE to generate a trajectory of appropriate length to fill it in. If the regrown segment contains the beginning or end of the original trajectory, such trial moves are also called *shooting moves*. Since we always regrow the trajectory using the SDE's dynamics these kinds of trial moves always generate a chain of correlated samples that are distributed according to $P(\mathbf{s})$. To account for the $U(\mathbf{s})$ term in our sampling distribution we pair such moves with an acceptance/rejection step.

We propose three possible strategies for creating trial moves that we are going to subsequently explain in more detail. All of these moves are symmetric, i.e. $T(\mathbf{s}_n \rightarrow \mathbf{s}_{n+1}) = T(\mathbf{s}_{n+1} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}_n)$.

1. Forward shooting: Choose a random point on the trajectory \mathbf{s}_n and *regrow* the trajectory from that point to the end. The proposal \mathbf{s}_{n+1} will coincide with \mathbf{s}_n from the start to the chosen random point. Accept the proposal with probability

$$A_{1,2}(\mathbf{s}_{n+1}, \mathbf{s}_n) = \min [1, e^{U(\mathbf{s}_{n+1})-U(\mathbf{s}_n)}] . \quad (4.33)$$

2. Backward shooting: Choose a random point on the trajectory \mathbf{s}_n and *regrow* the trajectory *backwards* from that point to the start. The proposal \mathbf{s}_{n+1} will coincide with \mathbf{s}_n from the chosen random point to the end. Accept the proposal with probability $A_{1,2}(\mathbf{s}_{n+1}, \mathbf{s}_n)$.
3. Internal regrowth: Choose *two* random points on the trajectory \mathbf{s}_n and *regrow* the trajectory *between* those points. The proposal \mathbf{s}_{n+1} will coincide with \mathbf{s}_n everywhere *except* the region between those two points. Accept the proposal with probability

$$A_3(\mathbf{s}_{n+1}, \mathbf{s}_n) = \min [1, e^{U(\mathbf{s}_{n+1})-U(\mathbf{s}_n)} p_{\text{connect}}] \quad (4.34)$$

where p_{connect} is an additional term that is needed to account for the fact that the regrown segment might not naturally connect well at both ends.

The first move is the simplest one since it straightforwardly regenerates the end of an existing trajectory. The Metropolis acceptance probability in eq. (4.33) is chosen such that asymptotically,

the sampling distribution converges towards $e^{-E(s)}$. Usually, the acceptance rate will be lower the longer the regrown segment is. Therefore, the first move is more likely to modify the parts of the trajectory close to the end. Consequently, it makes sense to use forward shooting together with backward shooting, if possible.

The second move is similar to the first one and shares the same acceptance probability. However to be able to do backward shooting we need to have signal dynamics that are time-reversible such that we can generate trajectories backwards in time. For example, if the signal obeys detailed balance, we can always reverse the stochastic dynamics [14]. Paired with forward shooting, we expect to generate a sequence of trajectories where both, segments close to the beginning and segments close to the end are modified. For long trajectories however there could still be cases where segments far away from both ends are very unlikely to get regrown. Therefore we also propose internal regrowth.

The third move regrows an internal segment of the trajectory. Notably this leads to an additional term p_{connect} in the acceptance probability in eq. (4.34). This term arises because we have to *connect* the last point of the regrown segment with the right edge of the whole in \mathbf{s}_n . If a segment was regrown in the time interval $[t_i, t_j]$ where t_1, \dots, t_N are the discretization points of \mathbf{s}_n , then we can write

$$p_{\text{connect}} = \frac{P(\mathbf{s}_{n+1}, t_{j-1} \rightarrow t_j)}{P(\mathbf{s}_n, t_{j-1} \rightarrow t_j)}. \quad (4.35)$$

The numerator gives the probability for the regrown trajectory to be connected, whereas the denominator gives the probability for the original trajectory \mathbf{s}_n to be connected at time t_j .

In this section we have presented three ideas for possible trial moves that we can combine with either thermodynamic integration or Wang-Landau sampling to use those methods for systems where the signal dynamics are given by a SDE.

4.6 Discussion

We have shown that methods originally developed for computing ensemble averages in statistical physics can be very successfully applied to the computation of marginal densities from a known joint density. Computing the marginal densities forms the basis for many Bayesian computations (including the computation of information theoretic quantities like the mutual information) and is therefore also relevant to a wide variety of researchers in fields outside of statistical physics.

Before we can make use the algorithms from statistical physics we have to map quantities like *energy* and the *partition function* to the corresponding probability densities. Once these terms are properly defined we suddenly have access to a wide variety of literature on statistical physics to aid us with efficient computation of the marginal entropy. Specifically we evaluated the usefulness of thermodynamic integration and the Wang-Landau algorithm for multivariate normal distributions.

Using Markov Chain Monte Carlo sampling together with thermodynamic integration we were able to achieve very good accuracy in estimates of $P(\mathbf{x})$ with a reasonable amount of computation time. We do not find any inherent bias in the estimates as we did for the brute-force Monte-Carlo estimate. The drawback of TI is that we need to produce samples using MCMC sampling. In practice to efficiently generate samples we need to find a good proposal distribution $T(\mathbf{s} \rightarrow \mathbf{s}')$ that yields proposals \mathbf{s}' that are *nearby* the previous signal \mathbf{s} such that there is on average a good chance that the proposal will be accepted according to eq. (4.18). On the other hand it is necessary for fast convergence that \mathbf{s}' is not *too close* to \mathbf{s} such that the sample chain explores a sufficiently large portion of the state space. While for our toy model it is relatively easy to come up with reasonable proposals, for stochastic trajectories this is less clear. Therefore we have proposed some ideas for possible trial moves in the space of trajectories. Even though TI seems to be a promising method for the computation of marginal densities, we also tested another technique that was originally developed in physics of condensed matter, the *Wang-Landau algorithm*.

While we can achieve a very precise estimate for the marginal density $P(\mathbf{x})$ using the estimated DOS from the Wang-Landau algorithm there remain some practical difficulties. For maximum efficiency and accuracy the different parameters affecting the procedure such as the required histogram flatness, the updating scheme of the f parameter, and the choice of potential bins have to be tuned for a given problem. After some tuning of these parameters for the Gaussian system for a fixed set of covariance matrices we still find the estimation to be at least one order of magnitude slower in CPU time compared to thermodynamic integration. Therefore, at least for the Gaussian system thermodynamic integration seems to be better suited to compute the marginal density.

With that said, we do expect the Wang-Landau procedure to perform especially well in cases were there are many local minima of the potential. Here using TI we might get “*stuck*” in a specific minimum and thus not sample all relevant states. Therefore we suggest that while TI should be the method of choice for the computation of the marginal density for high dimensional systems,

in specific cases it may make sense to try other approaches that are well-established in statistical physics, such as Wang-Landau.

Even if we can compute the mutual information more efficiently by using TI without estimating the DOS for individual responses it is worth noting that the intuitive picture behind the DOS shows very clearly why the brute-force Monte-Carlo estimates of the marginal density can converge very slowly. Particularly figs. 4.4 and 4.5 illustrate why more advanced simulation methods are unavoidable for the computation of marginal densities in high-dimensional state spaces. Looking at plots of the DOS can help to understand structural properties about the system at hand and is much easier to visualize than the high-dimensional state space.

5 Conclusion

We are developing a novel approach to estimate the mutual information between an environmental signal and a cellular response, fully taking into account the time-dependent stochastic dynamics. In principle, this approach is applicable to any biochemical signaling network that can be described by a master equation. One main issue that we found is the computation of accurate estimates of the marginal density which is defined by the integral $P(\mathbf{x}) = \int ds P(\mathbf{s}) P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$. By understanding the close relationship between that integral and the estimation of free energy differences, we were able to employ powerful computational methods originating in statistical physics. In that regard we have produced some promising results, yet it is clear that the work is not completed until we can demonstrate an accurate estimate for the mutual information for a simple biochemical network.

5.1 Summary of Main Results

To quantify the fidelity of biochemical networks, we motivated the computation of the *information rate* between a time-varying environmental signal and a cellular response. The information rate describes the (asymptotic) increase of mutual information (MI) with the duration of the signal. Using the very mild assumptions that a) the signal can be described by a stochastic differential equation, and b) the biochemical information processing network can be modeled by a master equation, we derived a general Monte Carlo procedure to compute the MI between signals and responses of arbitrary duration. It is based on our ability to generate independent sample signals and—for any given signal—the ability to generate an appropriate response. Crucially, we have shown, how for a given signal \mathbf{s} and response \mathbf{x} we can compute the so-called log-likelihood $\ln P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ using only terms from the master equation. One part of the Monte Carlo procedure consists in averaging these log-likelihoods for independently generated signals and responses. The

second part of the computation is much harder since it consists in computing the average over the logarithm of the integrated likelihood $\ln \int ds P(\mathbf{s}) P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$ for different responses.

An important contribution of this thesis is the careful analysis of the issues that can arise while numerically computing integrals of that form. If we merely use a standard Monte Carlo computation to evaluate the integrated likelihood we find that we consistently over-estimate the overall information rate. By approximating the signals and responses as Gaussian processes we were able to understand where this problem comes from. When randomly generating signals, as the duration grows it becomes increasingly unlikely to occasionally stumble upon a signal that contributes to the integral $\int ds P(\mathbf{s}) P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{s})$. It is easy to imagine that a given, time-varying response \mathbf{x} could only have arisen from a very narrow set of similar signals with the only difference between them being some small, insignificant fluctuations. In principle however, we have a huge variety of possible signal realizations that could have happened. We can understand that combing through the vast set of possible signals in search of that narrow subset of signals which contribute to the integral is very inefficient if done by brute force. It is not unlike searching for a needle in the haystack.

By having understood the problem we were able to infer what changes would lead to an improved estimate. The solution lies in the modification of the sampling strategy for the signals in such a way that we are more likely to find the strongly contributing ones. Pictorially speaking, this is perhaps comparable to the use of a metal proximity detector to help with the search of the needle. In the literature, there have been suggested multiple different but related ideas to modify sampling strategies in order to get more accurate results. While reviewing a few of the common methods we realized that many of these were inspired by techniques that originated in statistical physics for the estimation of free energy differences.

Thus, by changing the mathematical formulation of our problem we are able to see the computation of the marginal entropy akin to the computation of a free energy. Using this insight we have shown that using either of two well-known methods, *thermodynamic integration* and *Wang-Landau sampling* we are able to estimate the marginal likelihood much more efficiently for trajectories in the Gaussian approximation. While these ideas have not yet been tested on real stochastic trajectories, the results so far are very promising.

We propose that this thesis is an important step towards a general algorithmic framework to compute mutual information for arbitrary stochastic biological systems.

5.2 Outlook

We see a lot of opportunities for future work in the computational estimation of the mutual information. First of all, the method presented in this thesis is not yet complete and it will have to be shown that using Monte Carlo computations we can indeed make accurate estimates of the MI for arbitrary biochemical networks. To this end we intend to use thermodynamic integration and/or Wang-Landau sampling together with stochastically generated trajectories outside of the Gaussian approximation. It remains to be seen if the trial moves for trajectories proposed in sec. 4.5 lead to efficient estimates.

It is further of interest to come up with interesting biological systems to study using these methods. Since information processing is so abundant in life, many biochemical networks might only be understandable if we analyze their information processing capabilities. Analyzing the information efficiency of biochemical networks together with other important quantities such as nutrient usage, we can possibly understand tradeoffs that cells are making.

Lastly, while the Monte Carlo estimate discussed in this thesis is presented as a way to compute the mutual information for biochemical reaction networks, these are by far not the only systems that process information. Information processing is happening on all biological scales. Since the method that we present is quite general it would be very interesting to see extensions to other biological systems as for example neuronal networks.

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Declaration of Authorship

I hereby declare that this thesis is my own work, and that I have not used any sources and aids other than those stated in the thesis.

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